
Regional marine spatial planning to support Blue Growth while accounting for climate change

Project acronym:	ATLAS
Grant Agreement:	678760
Deliverable number:	Deliverable 6.3
Deliverable title:	Assessment of the utility of the MESMA generic framework to promote area-based management in N Atlantic case studies while accounting for climate change
Work Package:	6
Date of completion:	31/10/2020
Author:	<p>Lead Authors: Anthony Grehan, Oisín Callery (NUIG), Pablo Duran (IEO), David Stirling, Grant Campbell (MSS), Mar Sacau, Ana García-Alegre (IEO), Telmo Morato, Luís Rodrigues (IMAR/DOP), Ellen Kenchington (DFO), Joana Gafeira (BGS)</p> <p>Contributing Authors: Covadonga Orejas, José Luis Rueda, Miguel Hernandez Rosas (IEO) Lea-Anne Henry (UEDIN), Murray Roberts (UEDIN), Steve Ross (UNCW), Dick van Oevelen (NIOZ), Hrönn Egilsdóttir, Stefán Ragnarsson (IMR), Magali Combes, Sophie Arnaud-Haond, Sandrine Vaz, Lenaick Menot (IFREMER).</p>

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 678760 (ATLAS). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

List of ATLAS beneficiaries

Partner 1 University of Edinburgh (UEDIN)

Partner 2 Aarhus University (AU)

Partner 3 IMAR - University of the Azores (IMAR)

Partner 4 Regional Directorate of Sea Affairs, Azores Regional Government (IMAR/DOP)

Partner 5 NERC-British Geological Survey (BGS)

Partner 6 Gianni Consultancy (GC)

Partner 7 French Research Institute for Exploitation of the Sea (Ifremer)

Partner 8 Marine Scotland Science (MSS)

Partner 9 MARUM, University of Bremen (UniHB)

Partner 11 Royal Netherlands Institute for Sea Research (NIOZ)

Partner 12 Dynamic Earth (DE)

Partner 13 University of Oxford (UOX)

Partner 14 University College Dublin (UCD)

Partner 15 University College London (UCL)

Partner 16 National University of Ireland Galway (NUIG)

Partner 17 University of Liverpool (ULIV)

Partner 18 Syddansk Universitet (USD)

Partner 19 University of Tromsø – The Arctic University of Norway (UiT)

Partner 20 Scottish Association for Marine Science (SAMS)

Partner 21 Seascope Consultants (SC)

Partner 22 Instituto Espanol de Oceanografia (IEO)

Partner 23 University of North Carolina Wilmington (UNCW)

Partner 24 AquaTT

Partner 25 Iodine

List of acronyms

ABNJ - Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction

AMOC - Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation BBNJ - Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction

CEM - Conservation and Enforcement Measures EA - Enterprise Allocation

EAF - Ecosystem Approach Framework

EBSA - Ecologically or Biologically Significant Area

ECS - Extended Continental Shelf

EEZ - Exclusive Economic Zone

ENACW - Eastern North Atlantic Central Water

ICES - International Council for the Exploration of the Sea

IFMPs - Integrated Fisheries Management Plans

MAPAMA - Spanish Ministry for Agriculture, Fisheries, Food and Environment

MESMA - Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Areas project

MOW - Mediterranean Outflow Water

MPA - Marine Protected Area

MSFD – Marine Strategy Framework Directive

MSP - Maritime Spatial Planning

NAFO - Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization

NEAFC - North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission

RFMOs – Regional Fisheries Management Organisations

SAC – Special Area of Conservation

SEA - Strategic Environment Assessment

SFAs -Shrimp Fishing Areas

TAC - Total Allowable Catch

UNGA - United Nations General Assembly

VME - Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem

VMS - Vessel Monitoring Scheme

Table of Contents

1. Rationale	7
2. Porcupine Seabight and Bank Case Study	9
2.1 Context Setting.....	9
2.1.1. Set boundaries for Spatial Managed Area (SMA) Assessment (MESMA 1a)	9
2.1.2. Define goals and operational objectives for the SMA (MESMA 1b).....	11
2.2. Collate and map existing information.....	12
2.2.1. Identify ecosystem components (MESMA 2a).....	12
2.2.2. Identify pressures and impacts (MESMA 2b)	14
2.2.3. Identify existing management measures (MESMA 2c).....	16
2.3. Select indicators and benchmarks (MESMA Step 3)	17
2.3.1. Assessment of GES using the Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool.....	17
2.4. Conduct risk analysis (MESMA Step 3).....	19
2.4.1. Oil and gas risk analysis	19
2.4.2. Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of fishing activities.....	19
2.5. Assessment of findings against operational objectives: Blue Growth scenarios (MESMA Step 5)	21
2.6. Evaluation of management effectiveness and recommend adaptations to current management in the light of climate change (MESMA Steps 6 and 7).....	35
2.6.1. Expanded MPA network and climate change	35
2.6.2. Oil and gas exploration and climate change	38
2.7. Governance (MESMA Step 8).....	38
2.7.1. The role of Systematic Conservation Planning in Maritime Spatial Planning	38
2.7.2. Future Proofing Conservation Requirements.....	39
2.8. References.....	40
3. Flemish Cap Case Study	43
3.1. Context Setting.....	43
3.1.1. Set boundaries for Spatial Managed Area (SMA) Assessment (MESMA 1a)	43
3.1.2. Define goals and operational objectives for the SMA (MESMA 1b).....	45
3.2. Collate and map existing information.....	46
3.2.1. Identify ecosystem components (MESMA 2a) and human activities, pressures and impacts (MESMA 2b).....	46
3.2.2. Identify existing management measures (MESMA 2c).....	48
3.3. Select indicators and benchmarks (MESMA Step 3)	50
3.3.1. Seabed litter	50
3.4. Conduct risk analysis (MESMA Step 4).....	52
3.4.1. Oil and gas risk analysis	52
3.4.2. Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of fishing activities.....	53

3.5. Assessment of findings against operational objectives: Blue Growth scenarios (MESMA Step 5)	55
3.5.1. Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of an existing or expanded network of marine protected areas while maintaining current fisheries at close to current levels.	55
3.5.2. Assess potential future impacts of oil and gas developments at the Flemish Cap.	60
3.6. Evaluation of management effectiveness and recommend adaptations to current management in the light of climate change (MESMA Steps 6 and 7).....	63
3.6.1. Expanded MPA network and climate change	63
3.6.2. Oil and gas exploration and climate change	65
3.7. Governance (MESMA Step 8).....	66
3.7.1. Utility of MSP in the NAFO Regulatory Area	66
3.7.2. MSP as a potential tool to help resolve conflicts: connection with Blue Economy - Blue Growth.....	67
3.7.3. Reflections on ocean governance: VMEs are closed to fishing but open to oil and gas	67
3.7.4. Lack of an appropriate authority needed to undertake MSP in ABJN	68
3.8. Conclusions.....	68
3.9. Acknowledgements.....	69
3.10. Bibliography	69
4. Rockall Bank Case Study.....	71
4.1. Context Setting.....	71
4.1.1. Set boundaries for Spatial Managed Area (SMA) Assessment (MESMA 1a)	71
4.1.2. Define goals and operational objectives for the SMA (MESMA 1b).....	72
4.2. Collate and map existing information.....	73
4.2.1. Identify ecosystem components (MESMA 2a).....	73
4.2.2. Identify human activities, pressures and impacts (MESMA 2b)	77
4.2.3. Identify existing management measures (MESMA 2c).....	79
4.3. Select indicators and benchmarks (MESMA Step 3)	83
4.3.1. MSFD Indicators.....	83
4.3.2. MSFD in the deep-sea.....	83
4.3.3. Good Environmental Status at the Rockall Bank	84
4.4. Conduct risk analysis (MESMA Step 4).....	85
4.4.1. Oil and gas risk analysis	85
4.4.2. Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of fishing activities.....	85
4.5. Assessment of findings against operational objectives: Blue Growth scenarios (MESMA Step 5)	87

4.5.1. Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of an existing or expanded network of marine protected areas while maintaining current fisheries at close to current levels.	87
4.5.2. Assess potential future impacts of oil and gas developments – Scenario 3.....	93
4.6. Evaluation of management effectiveness and recommend adaptations to current management in the light of climate change (MESMA Steps 6 and 7).....	97
4.7. Governance (MESMA Step 8).....	99
4.8. References.....	100
5. Summary Conclusions	103
5.1. MESMA Marine Spatial Planning Framework.....	103
5.2. Systematic Conservation Planning	103
5.2.1. Conserving the geophysical stage.....	103
5.2.2. Protecting climate refugia.....	103
5.2.3. Enhancing regional connectivity.....	104
5.2.4. Sustaining ecosystem process and function.....	104
5.3. Capitalizing on opportunities emerging in response to climate change.	104
5.4. References.....	116
Appendix	117

Assessment of the utility of the MESMA generic framework to promote area-based management in N Atlantic case studies while accounting for climate change

1. Rationale

This deliverable reports on testing of the generic Marine Spatial Planning framework (Figure 1) developed by the EU FP7 Monitoring and Evaluation of Spatially Managed Areas (MESMA) project (Stelzenmüller *et al.*, 2013)¹ to assess spatially managed areas (SMAs).

Figure 1. The flowchart shows proposed framework to monitor and evaluate spatially managed areas (SMAs) through seven key steps (Stelzenmüller *et al.* 2013).

The different ATLAS Case Studies represent a wide range of biogeographic, regulatory and jurisdictional situations encountered across the Atlantic. SMAs are discrete geographic regions that can be defined at different spatial scales, but where a spatial management framework (e.g. MSP) is either in place, under development, or potentially being considered. The main objective of this deliverable is to assess whether the existing science base is sufficient to support theoretical regional/local SMAs that can help balance the conduct/development of human activities with protection of the environment. Key questions to address are:

- Is there sufficient data to apply a maritime spatial planning approach in the deep-sea?
- If not, can we fill the gaps?
- Can we use basin scale planning to inform local plans?

¹ Stelzenmüller *et al.* (2013). Monitoring and evaluation of spatially managed areas: A generic framework for implementation of ecosystem based marine management and its application. *Marine Policy* 37: 149–164. doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.04.012.

It should be made clear at the outset, that this is a theoretical exercise as ATLAS has no legal competence or mandate to produce marine spatial plans and undertook no consultation with stakeholders in that regard with one exception. One of our partners, IMAR/DOP, after the start of ATLAS, was formally contracted to: i) produce systematic conservation planning scenarios for the Azores deep-sea and, ii) following a request by the Regional Government of the Azores, use systematic conservation planning to develop various scenarios to evaluate the potential impact of fisheries closed areas on the Mar da Prata seamount. The reports are attached as a contribution to this Deliverable in the accompanying Deliverable 6.3 Appendix.

2. Porcupine Seabight and Bank Case Study

2.1 Context Setting

2.1.1. Set boundaries for Spatial Managed Area (SMA) Assessment (MESMA 1a)

2.1.1.1. Description of the Case Study Area

The Porcupine Bank separates the Porcupine Seabight from the Rockall Trough and Rockall Bank. The summit of the Porcupine Bank is shallow lying at 145 m water depth and is generally broad and flat, although some structures from the underlying basement rocks can be seen emerging in places. The eastern slope, towards the Porcupine Seabight, is gentle whereas the southern, western and northern slopes towards the Rockall Trough are steep. Along the western and northern Porcupine Bank, the slope- break from the flat summit area onto the steep slopes occurs at a remarkably consistent water depth of approximately 450 m and is generally marked by a prolonged escarpment. The western and northern slopes of the Porcupine Bank facing the Rockall Trough are characterised by irregularly spaced canyons and the south-western slope of the Porcupine Bank is especially steep and eroded (Dorschel et al. 2010).

The waters around Ireland are some of the most productive fishing grounds in the world². In 2004, an estimated 1.5 million tonnes of fish (worth €1.4 Billion) were landed from these waters by the international fishing fleets, mainly from Spain, France, UK, Norway, Holland and Ireland. The main fish species caught are mackerel, horse mackerel, blue whiting, herring, cod, whiting, haddock, saithe, hake, megrim, monkfish plaice, sole and *Nephrops*. They also contain some of the most important fish spawning and nursery areas in the North Atlantic. The main mackerel, horse mackerel and blue whiting spawning grounds for the North Atlantic occur off the west of Ireland as do important spawning areas for hake and megrim off the south west of Ireland.

2.1.1.2. Institutional Landscape

At present, there is no single integrated management plan for the Porcupine Seabight and Bank area. But Ireland is in the process of developing a national Maritime Spatial Plan in accordance with the EU Maritime Spatial Planning Directive. The Government published a roadmap in 2017: Towards a ‘Marine Spatial Plan for Ireland’³ with four stages:

- Stage 1, the activation phase during which the Government’s proposed approach to developing MSP was announced and initial contact made with stakeholders. This ran until end 2017.
- Stage 2, the main development stage, ran until early 2020. It involved preparation and publishing for public consultation a Draft National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF)⁴ and associated environmental reports.

²

<https://oar.marine.ie/bitstream/handle/10793/601/Biologically%20Sensitive%20Area.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>

³ www.housing.gov.ie/sites/default/files/publications/files/towards_a_marine_spatial_plan_for_ireland.pdf

⁴ www.housing.gov.ie/sites/default/files/public-consultation/files/draft_national_marine_planning_framework_final.pdf

- Stage 3 is the finalisation phase during which the Draft NMPF and associated environmental reports will be amended as required based on the feedback received in the public consultation. The final NMPF and associated environmental reports will be prepared for submission to Government and adoption by the Oireachtas (the legislature of Ireland) in 2020 before forwarding to the European Commission ahead of the March 2021 deadline set out under the Directive.
- Stage 4 is implementation, monitoring, enforcement and review commencing on adoption of the NMPF.

The Oireachtas Pre-Legislative Scrutiny of the Marine Planning and Development Management Bill is currently taking place (December 2020).

The Programme for Government – Our Shared Future 2020⁵ sets out its support for the *EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030* and will develop comprehensive legislation for the identification, designation, and management of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) in Irish territorial waters. The Government is committed to realising Ireland’s outstanding target of 10% under the Marine Strategy Framework Directive as soon as is practical and will aim for 30% of marine protected areas by 2030. This will be done using best available science and in close consultation with all stakeholders, in particular the fishing industry, as well as environmental and community representatives. The Government will in addition examine the potential establishment of an offshore maritime area as Ireland’s seventh national park and as a contribution to the expanded MPA network. The Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage recently assembled an expert group to prepare a report outlining the options for expanding Ireland’s Marine Protected Area network (MPAAG, 2020).

The Government will prioritise the passage of a balanced and Aarhus Convention compliant Marine and Planning and Development Management (MPDM) Bill through the Oireachtas. It intends to publish Ireland’s first ever marine spatial planning policy, setting out a clear vision for the future development of our marine planning system in consultation with the public and stakeholders. It will then bring forward Ireland’s first ever planning system for the development of Ireland’s maritime area under the National Marine Planning Framework (NMPF). These two documents will form the basis for Project Ireland Marine 2040, the Government’s long-term overarching strategy to manage Ireland’s seas for the benefit of all its people.

⁵ www.greenparty.ie/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/ProgrammeForGovernment_June2020_Final.pdf

2.1.1.3. Porcupine and Porcupine Bank Spatial Managed Area

The spatial managed area (SMA) for this case study encompasses the area between the Territorial Sea boundary (12 nautical miles from the baseline) and the Irish 200 mile EEZ boundary (Figure 2. 1).

Figure 2. 1. Location of the Porcupine Seabight and Bank case study showing the location of Ireland's offshore reef Special Areas of Conservation and fisheries Biologically Sensitive Area.

2.1.2. Define goals and operational objectives for the SMA (MESMA 1b)

2.1.2.1. Blue Growth Goals

The blue growth goal here is to provide a framework for the sustainable use of natural resources, goods and services derived from the Porcupine Seabight and Bank area, including oil and gas extraction, while ensuring the maintenance of the structure, functioning, productivity and diversity of the area's ecosystems.

2.1.2.2. Operational Objectives

- Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of an existing or expanded network of marine protected areas.
- Maintain current fisheries at or close to current levels of activity while taking into account wider ecosystem impacts.
- Assess the potential impacts of oil and gas developments.

2.2. Collate and map existing information

2.2.1. Identify ecosystem components (MESMA 2a)

2.2.1.1. Seafloor habitats/species

Figure 2. 2. MSFD broad-scale habitat types with confidence assessment.

Figure 2. 3. Predicted distribution of six VME indicator species (Morato et al. 2020).

2.2.1.2. Fish spawning, nursery and fishing grounds

Figure 2. 4. Principal fish spawning, nursery and fishing grounds.

Figure 2. 5. Predicted distribution of six fish species (Morato et al. 2020).

2.2.1.3. Ship-wrecks as artificial reefs

Figure 2. 6. Location of Infomar mapped shipwrecks.

2.2.2. Identify pressures and impacts (MESMA 2b)

Figure 2. 7a. Various legislative, socio-economic and ecological datasets

Figure 2.7b. Value per ICES rectangle and deep sea demersal species landings in the Porcupine, Ireland (from ATLAS Deliverable 6.2).

2.2.3. Identify existing management measures (MESMA 2c)

2.2.3.1. Conservation measures

2.2.3.1.1. Habitats Directive

Ireland currently has 6 offshore Special Areas of Conservation protecting biogenic and geogenic reef habitat as listed in Annex 2 of the EU Habitats Directive. Biogenic reefs are formed principally by two framework building corals, *Lophelia pertusa* and *Madrepora oculata*, and reefs tend to be found atop topographically high particularly carbonate mounds which are found in clusters in the Irish offshore. These carbonate mounds can be up to 400m in height and are composed of the sediment buried skeletons of corals. Geogenic reef is classified by the 2013 Natura 2000 Interpretation Manual of European Union Habitats⁶ as including a variety of hard substrates provided by sea mounts, vertical rock walls, horizontal ledges, overhangs, pinnacles, gullies, ridges, sloping or flat bed rock, broken rock and boulder and cobble fields. Four reef locations were proposed as Sites of Community Importance (SCI) in 2006 (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Together with two additional SCI, all six were designated as Special Areas of Conservation in 2016. The SACs cover an area of almost 5000 km².

Table 2.1. List of the six Irish offshore Special Areas of Conservation protecting Natura 2000 reefs.

Special Area of Conservation (SAC) Name	Site Code	Area (km ²)	Area (ha)	Date proposed as Site of Community Importance	Date designated as SAC
Belgica Mound Province	IE0002327	411	41090.4	2006	2016
Hovland Mound Province	IE0002328	1,086	108655.0	2006	2016
South-west Porcupine Bank	IE0002329	329	32929.9	2006	2016
Porcupine Bank Canyon	IE0003001	781	78110.0	2012	2016
North-west Porcupine Bank	IE0002330	716	71629.7	2006	2016
South-east Rockall Bank	IE0003002	1487	148790.0	2011	2016
	TOTAL	4810 km ²	481205 ha		

The current extent of offshore reef protected by SACs has however been deemed insufficient by the European Commission and efforts are underway to identify additional reef areas for designation largely based on data collected during EMFF funded 'SeaRover' ROV surveys conducted between 2017 and 2020.

2.2.3.1.2. Fisheries Closures

In 2003, the EU Commission established a "Biologically Sensitive Area (BSA)" off the south west of Ireland (Council Regulation (EC) No 1954/2003) (Figure 2. 1) given that there are important juvenile fish nursery particularly for hake in the area. In 2003, the EU also

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/legislation/habitatsdirective/docs/Int_Manual_EU28.pdf

established a specific fishing effort regime inside the BSA and outside the BSA for demersal fishing vessels as well as scallop and crab fisheries (i.e. different fishing effort regulations apply inside and outside of the box).

In 2016, the EU Commission enacted new legislation, (EU) 2016/2336, regulating access to deep-sea fisheries. Together with (EU) 734/2008, the new deep-sea access regime requires that vulnerable marine ecosystems are protected from the adverse impacts of bottom fishing gears. The regulations apply to all bottom gears used in EU and Irish waters below 400m including bottom trawls, dredges, bottom-set gillnets, bottom-set longlines, pots and traps. Deep sea fishing authorisations to use any bottom gears may normally only be granted for fishing activities within the areas that were fished with bottom gears during the reference period 2009-2011 (the fisheries “footprint”). Outside of the fisheries footprint, deep-sea fishing authorisations to use any bottom gears may be granted only if an impact assessment demonstrates that the protection of VMEs will not be compromised. However, bottom trawling at depths >800 metres is prohibited in all areas (inside and outside the footprint). Implementing acts to establish a list of areas where VMEs are known to occur or are likely to occur should have been drawn up by 13 January 2018 in order to prevent significant adverse impacts of VMEs in those areas with the list of areas subject to annual review. The European Commission has now requested advice from the International Council for Exploration of the Seas (ICES) to advance this process; work is ongoing (ICES, 2019).

A Common Fisheries Policy technical conservation measure permanently banning bottom trawling from the original four offshore SACs (2.2.3.1.1 above) is now in place (Regulation (EU) No 2019/1241). While Council Regulation (EC) No 2270/2004 that prohibits directed fisheries from targeting *Hoplostethus atlanticus* (orange roughy) aggregations above carbonate mounds along the western Porcupine Bank, continues to confer protection on the coral reefs found there.

2.3. Select indicators and benchmarks (MESMA Step 3)

2.3.1. Assessment of GES using the Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool

In the recently published article (Kazanidis et al., 2020), ATLAS partners sought to contribute to the implementation of the MSFD in the deep North Atlantic by carrying out an assessment of the environmental status of nine strategically-selected North Atlantic deep-sea areas. Focusing on MSFD descriptors: D1 (Biodiversity is maintained), D3 (The population of commercial fish species is healthy), D4 (Elements of food webs ensure long-term abundance and reproduction), D6 (The sea floor integrity ensures functioning of the ecosystem) and D10 (Marine litter does not cause harm), as particularly relevant for the deep sea (Kazanidis et al., 2020), the “Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool” (NEAT)⁷ was used to assess the progress made towards achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) in each of the nine selected case studies. To facilitate an integrated assessment of marine environmental status, NEAT can be used to consider data from various indicators over different spatial and temporal scales; the tool uses a nested hierarchical structure of spatial assessment units (SAUs), habitats and ecosystem components, and interconnected indicators linked to MSFD descriptors to determine an environmental score for individual SAUs based on a 5-class scale (bad, poor, moderate, good, high).

⁷ <http://www.devotes-project.eu/neat/>

In the this case study, SAUs were determined on the basis of clustering areas of similar depth bands with reference to MSFD Broad Benthic Habitat classification (Figure 2.8A). In 8 of the 9 ATLAS case studies in which NEAT was applied the indicator “areal extent of human affected area” (indicating the deep-sea areas affected by demersal fisheries) was found to be a particularly useful indicator, as in this case study. This was largely due to good data availability for this indicator, but also because the impact of demersal fisheries on benthic habitats is at least one (if not up to three) orders of magnitude greater than any other human activity impacting benthic habitats in the deep sea (Benn et al., 2010; Orejas et al., 2020). A nested environmental status assessment was then conducted using the “areal extent of human affected area” indicator in NEAT to determine scores for each SAU (Figure 2.8B).

Table 2.2. Spatial Assessment Units used in the offshore GES assessment.

Spatial Assessment Unit (SAU)	SAU Level	Parent ID	Area (km ²)	Description
SAU 1	1	1	589600	Irish Continental Shelf >200m Depth
▶ SAU 1-1	2	1	128700	Rockall Trough
▶ SAU 1-2	2	1	35500	Porcupine Seabight
▶ SAU 1-3	2	1	213900	Abyssal Plain
SAU 2	2	1	114400	Irish Mainland Shelf
▶ SAU 2-1	3	2	40000	Porcupine Ridge
▶ SAU 2-1-1	4	2-1	4700	Porcupine Bank
▶ SAU 2-2	3	2	15400	Slyne Ridge
▶ SAU 3	2	1	97100	Rockall Plateau
▶ SAU 3-1	3	3	31300	Rockall Bank

The results indicate that the Irish offshore is generally in good to high environmental status with shallow areas on the Porcupine Bank and around the Seabight, more subject to fishing having moderate status.

The recently published 2019 Article 17 Update to Ireland’s Marine Strategy Assessment⁸ has assessed Descriptor 6 (sea-floor integrity) using the criteria of physical loss. The report concludes that Ireland is achieving Good Environmental Status (GES) because the extent of physical loss within the maritime area is lower than any potential threshold value. It should be noted that for the purposes of the assessment, physical loss is defined as any human-induced permanent alteration of the physical habitat from which recovery is impossible, within one 6-year MSFD cycle. Historical physical loss such as occurred in the early 2000s when coral reefs on a number of carbonate mounds were removed during demersal fishing for orange roughy (Grehan et al. 2004) is not accounted for even when no recovery has taken place.

⁸ https://www.housing.gov.ie/sites/default/files/publications/files/appendices_-_assessment_sheets_.pdf

Figure 2.8. A: Map of MSFD Broad Benthic Habitats used to delineate the SAUs for the assessment of GES alongside B: scores of environmental status obtained from the NEAT analysis.

2.4. Conduct risk analysis (MESMA Step 3)

2.4.1. Oil and gas risk analysis

160 Exploration and Appraisal wells have been drilled in the Irish offshore since 1970. There have been four commercial gas discoveries. In addition, there have been approximately 11 key oil, gas and condensate discoveries but none have yet led to commercial developments. Ireland's Kinsale gas field stopped gas production on the 5th of July 2020 when all the gas reserves in the various fields were depleted. The wells will now be permanently plugged with cement and the associated facilities (platforms, pipelines, cables, subsea structures and onshore terminal) will be decommissioned. The Corrib gas field off the northwest coast of Ireland (Mayo) continues to produce natural gas. In 2019, the Irish Government announced it would phase out oil and gas production and no new hydrocarbon exploration licences would be granted in a response to climate change. Existing licences and options for oil and gas remain valid.

2.4.2. Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of fishing activities

The impact of multiple environmental pressures caused by demersal trawling was subjected to a cumulative environmental assessment using a workflow and decision tool developed by Callery et al. (2020). By linking the JNCC Marine Pressures Activities Database (PAD) with spatial data layers of fishing activity derived from fishing vessel automatic identification system (AIS) location data (Kroodsmas et al., 2018), a map of all pressures associated with demersal trawling was compiled. A second map combining sensitivities to individual pressures for all habitats in the Porcupine SMA was compiled using the habitat sensitivity scores provided by the Marine Evidence-based Sensitivity Assessment (MarESA) (Callery et al.

2020), with the combination of sensitivity and pressure intensity providing a cumulative impact index for each location following the methodology developed by Halpern et al. (2008).

Figure 2.9. Comparison of the average spatial footprint of bottom contacting fishing activity in the Porcupine Bank and Seabight case study from the year 2016 based on: A) Swept Area Ratio (SAR) as calculated from analysis of VMS/logbook data (ICES,2018), and B) the associated cumulative impacts on benthic habitats resulting from concomitant pressures.

Fishing activity in Irish waters is quite intense in the Celtic Sea and along the edge of the Porcupine Seabight and on the east side of the Porcupine Bank (Figure 2.9A). The highest

impact from fishing is along the edge of the Porcupine Seabight and west of the Porcupine Bank (Figure 2.9B).

2.5. Assessment of findings against operational objectives: Blue Growth scenarios (MESMA Step 5)

2.5.1. *Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of an existing or expanded network of marine protected areas while maintaining current fisheries at close to current levels.*

2.5.1.1. Baseline assessment of the effectiveness of current conservation measures

Figure 2.10. Baseline assessment of the degree of protection offered by existing conservation management measures in the Porcupine to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicate habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The CFP Deep-Sea Access Regime, (EU) 2016/2336, prohibits demersal trawling below 800m. The baseline assessment of current conservation measures (Figure 2.10) includes both Special Areas of Conservation and the seabed below 800m (dark green in bar charts). The SACs established to protect reefs also partially protect VME species. Removing fishing pressure below 800m substantially increases the protection of VMEs.

2.5.1.2. Systematic conservation planning

Achieving a defined conservation objective subject to various spatial and socioeconomic constraints – i.e. solving a **conservation problem** – is a task which may be facilitated greatly with the use of any one of a number of available software packages, for example *Marxan* (including *Marxan with Zones* and *Marxan Connect*) (Ball and Possingham, 2000; Daigle et al., 2020; Watts et al., 2009), *RobOff* (Pouzols and Moilanen, 2013), *Zonation* (Moilanen et al., 2009), *ResNet* (Garson et al., 2002), *ConsNet* (Sarkar et al., 2009) and *C-Plan* (Pressey et al., 2009) to name a few. Recently, the *prioritizr* package (Hanson et al., 2017) has been developed to facilitate SCP using the highly extensible open source R programming language. *Prioritizr* uses exact integer linear programming (ILP) solvers to identify solutions to **conservation problems** in a much shorter timeframe than software like *Marxan* (which use simulated annealing (SA)), and furthermore solutions identified using the ILP approach implemented by *prioritizr* have been demonstrated to be 12-30% more optimal than solutions identified using SA (Schuster et al., 2020).

2.5.1.2.1. SCP Terminology

To explain how *prioritizr* works, it would be useful to first be familiar with some of the nomenclature used in constructing and solving **conservation problems**, not just for the *prioritizr* package, but in the field of SCP in general. The following is a non-exhaustive glossary (in logical rather than alphabetical order) of important terms used in SCP, and how these terms were interpreted for the SCP exercise undertaken as part of this ATLAS deliverable (nomenclature with specific interpretations when used with reference to SCP are highlighted **thus** throughout this document).

2.5.1.2.2. Conservation Features

Conservation features are defined in the *Marxan Good Practices Handbook* as “*measurable, spatially definable component of biodiversity that is to be conserved within a reserve network*” (Ardron et al., 2010). A **conservation feature**, then, is a specific habitat, species, or other ecological/cultural feature of interest that a marine planner may wish to have represented in a given reserve system. **Conservation Features** are often the spatial outputs of Species Distribution Models (SDMs) (Schmiing et al., 2015), maps of biotopes and physical habitats (Evans et al., 2015; Howell, 2010), or other potentially important features (from a biological or cultural perspective) such as shipwrecks (Ekeboom et al., 2008). For this deliverable, the SDM spatial data layers produced in ATLAS Work Package 3 – i.e. predicted distributions of six commercially important deep-sea fishes and six deep-sea cold-water corals in the North Atlantic Ocean) under present (see Figure 2. 11 and Figure 2.12) and future environmental conditions were used to identify areas of essential habitat for fish and VME indicator taxa, as well as areas predicted to be “climate refugia” (sensu Keppel and Wardell-Johnson, 2012) for these species. In addition to the SDM outputs of ATLAS Work Package 3, data relating to the spatial distribution of benthic habitats (as classified under the European Nature Information System (EUNIS) hierarchical habitat classification schema) were obtained from the EMODnet seabed habitats data portal (<https://emodnet.eu/en/seabed-habitats>); these data comprise part of the EUSeaMap (Populus et al., 2017), currently in its third phase. Using the EUSeaMap data ensured that there were no “gaps” in any area of the ATLAS case studies in the North-East Atlantic – i.e. there were no areas which did not contain at least 1 **conservation feature**; this was in an attempt to ensure that any MPA network identified using SCP would be as close to “*ecologically representative*” (as specified by the CBD) as possible given current data limitations in the deep-sea. For ATLAS case studies in the North-West Atlantic – i.e. areas not

covered by the EUSeaMap – predicted EUNIS habitats were used as *conservation features* based on a machine learning based classification made on the basis of predicted species distributions (Work Package 3) being a proxy/predictor of habitat type - this habitat modelling approach is described in detail in ATLAS Milestone Report 30: *Mapping the Cumulative Effect of Bottom Fisheries on Benthic Habitats in 12 ATLAS Case Study Areas*. Finally, bona fide records of VME habitat from the ICES VME database (<https://vme.ices.dk/webservices.aspx>) as well as spatial data on the distribution of habitats on the OSPAR List of Threatened and/or Declining Species and Habitats (<https://odims.ospar.org/>) were used to fulfil the criteria of protecting “*sites of particular importance for biodiversity*”, as specified in the CBD’s Post-2020 Biodiversity Framework. A table summarising the *conservation features* used in these local SCP exercises is included below (Table 2. 3).

VME Indicator Taxa	Note	Conservation Feature	Conservation Feature ID
<i>Lophelia pertusa</i>			1,2
<i>Madrepora oculata</i>	Scleractinian corals that form aragonite skeletons	Present day distribuitons and climate refugia identified in ATLAS Work Package 3	3,4
<i>Desmophyllum dianthus</i>			5,6
<i>Acanella arbuscula</i>	Octocorals forming calcitic axial skeletons		7,8
<i>Acanthogorgia armata</i>			9,10
<i>Paragorgia arborea</i>			11,12
Fish occuring in depths > 200m			
	Common name		
<i>Coryphaenoides rupestris</i>	Round nose grenadier		13,14
<i>Gadus morhua</i>	Atlantic Cod		15,16
<i>Helicolenus dactylopterus</i>	Blackbelly rosefish	Present day distribuitons and climate refugia identified in ATLAS Work Package 3	17,18
<i>Hippoglossoides platessoides</i>	American plaice		19,20
<i>Reinhardtius hippoglossoides</i>	Greenland halibut		21,22,
<i>Sebastes mentella.</i>	Beaked redfish		23,24
EUNIS Habitats			
	Description		
A6	Deep-sea bed		25
A6.11	Deep-sea rock		26
A6.2	Deep-sea mixed substrata		27
A6.3	Deep-sea sand		28
A6.4	Deep-sea muddy sand		29
A6.5	Deep-sea mud		30
A6.51	Mediterranean communities of bathyal muds		31
A6.511	Facies of sandy muds with <i>Thenea muricata</i>		32
A6.52	Communities of abyssal muds		33
A5	Sublittoral sediment		34
A5.13	Infralittoral coarse sediment		35
A5.14	Circalittoral coarse sediment		36
A5.15	Deep circalittoral coarse sediment		37

A5.23	Infralittoral fine sand	38
A5.24	Infralittoral muddy sand	39
A5.25	Circalittoral fine sand	40
A5.26	Circalittoral muddy sand	41
A5.27	Deep circalittoral sand	42
A5.33	Infralittoral sandy mud	43
A5.34	Infralittoral fine mud	44
A5.35	Circalittoral sandy mud	45
A5.36	Circalittoral fine mud	46
A5.37	Deep circalittoral mud	47
A5.38	Mediterranean biocoenosis of muddy detritic bottoms	48
A5.39	Mediterranean biocoenosis of coastal terrigenous muds	49
A5.43	Infralittoral mixed sediment	50
A5.44	Circalittoral mixed sediment	51
A5.45	Deep circalittoral mixed sediments	52
A5.46	Mediterranean biocoenosis of coastal detritic bottoms	53
A5.47	Mediterranean communities of shelf-edge detritic bottoms	54
A5.535	[Posidonia] beds	55
A5.5353	Facies of dead "mattes" of [Posidonia oceanica]	56
A4	Circalittoral rock and other hard substrata	57
A4.1	Atlantic and Mediterranean high energy circalittoral rock	58
A4.12	Sponge communities on deep circalittoral rock	59
A4.2	Atlantic and Mediterranean moderate energy circalittoral rock	60
A4.27	Faunal communities on deep moderate energy circalittoral rock	61
A4.3	Atlantic and Mediterranean low energy circalittoral rock	62
A4.33	Faunal communities on deep low energy circalittoral rock	63
A4.4	Baltic exposed circalittoral rock	64
A4.5	Baltic moderately exposed circalittoral rock	65
A4.6	Baltic sheltered Circalittoral rock	66
A3	Infralittoral rock and other hard substrata	67
A3.1	Atlantic and Mediterranean high energy infralittoral rock	68
A3.2	Atlantic and Mediterranean moderate energy infralittoral rock	69
A3.3	Atlantic and Mediterranean low energy infralittoral rock	70
A3.4	Baltic exposed infralittoral rock	71
A3.5	Baltic moderately exposed infralittoral rock	72
A3.6	Baltic sheltered infralittoral rock	73

ICES VME Habitats

Anemone aggregations	74
Cold-water coral reef	75
Coral gardens	76
Deep-sea sponge aggregations	77

Mud and sand emergent fauna	78
Seapen fields	79

OSPAR Threatened and Declining Habitats	Note	
Deep-sea sponge aggregations	Point and Polygon records	80,81
Lophelia pertusa reefs	Point and Polygon records	82,83
Maerl beds		84
Carbonate mounds	Point and Polygon records	85,86
Seamounts	Point and Polygon records	87,88
Coral gardens	Point and Polygon records	89,90
Oceanic ridges with hydrothermal vents/fields		91
Sea-pen and burrowing megafauna communities	Point and Polygon records	92

Table 2. 3. List of conservation features used in ATLAS local SCP exercise.

Figure 2. 11. Habitat suitability index predicted under present-day environmental conditions for commercially important deep-sea fishes in the North Atlantic Ocean using an ensemble modelling approach.

Figure 2.12. Habitat suitability index predicted under present-day environmental conditions for cold-water corals in the North Atlantic Ocean using an ensemble modelling approach.

2.5.1.2.3. Conservation Targets

A **conservation target** is the amount of each **conservation feature** that a marine planner wishes to be included within the SCP reserve solution – this can be an absolute target, e.g. 1000km² of a given habitat, or a proportional target, e.g. 30% of the areal extent or a habitat within the entire spatially managed area. Aichi Target 11 of the CBD’s Strategic Plan for Biodiversity, 2011-2020 states that biodiversity should be protected by means of “*ecologically representative*” systems of protected areas and OECMs, while the Post-2020 Biodiversity Framework specifies the need to protect at least 30% of land and sea areas, with at least 10% under strict protection. These criteria, when considered together, could be interpreted thus: if the goal of the MPA network should be to protect X% of the extents of **each conservation feature** in a given SMA (i.e. to produce an “*ecologically representative*” solution), to achieve this it will be necessary to protect at least X% of that SMA, and (implicitly) almost certainly more than X%, depending on how the distributions of all **conservation features** overlap. In the SCP exercise conducted for this ATLAS deliverable, **conservation targets** of 10%, 30%, and

50% for all *conservation features* were investigated as “baseline” SCP scenarios, as well as scenarios exploring the multi-target 2030 conservation scenario described in the CBD’s Post-2020 Biodiversity Framework. These SCP scenarios are discussed in further detail later in this text.

2.5.1.2.4. Planning Area/Planning Units

The *planning area (PA)* is, quite simply, the area for which SCP is carried out. It is important that users be cognizant of the fact that the *PA* is considered as a microcosm by the SCP software, and solutions obtained will reflect this, being made in total isolation to areas outside the *PA*; when constructing *conservation problems* users should take this into account – for example, if a *PA* contains regions which are of importance on a larger scale than that of the *PA* itself, adjustments need to be made ensure that the formulation of the *conservation problem* reflects this accordingly. For this exercise – local SCP – the bounds of each ATLAS study were considered as discrete *PAs*. The *PAs* were themselves divided up into a planning grid comprised of many small cells or *planning units (PUs)*; the SCP software attempts to select (i.e. conserve) the set of *PUs* which best meets the selected *conservation targets*. All of the available data on *conservation features* within the *PA* is summarised on a per *PU* basis – a process commonly referred to as zonal statistics – and the potential contribution of a single *PU* to meeting a given *conservation target* is thus easily enumerated. It is possible to both “lock in” and “lock out” *PUs* to ensure that they will be present or absent, respectively, from the SCP solution. This is useful, for example, to ensure that any existing MPAs will be present in the SCP solution, or that areas which are not suitable for conservation (e.g. an area zoned for an activity mutually exclusive to conservation such as aggregate extraction) will not be available for selection by the SCP software. Locking in/out *PUs* can have significant effects on the resulting solution – for example, *conservation targets* may already be met or exceeded by the existing MPA network with the *PA*, making further attempts at SCP redundant. Also, because the SCP software will seek (where possible) to form contiguous MPAs (discussed in further detail later in this text), locked in *PUs* can function as “seeds” about which MPAs will form (provided the area surrounding the locked-in *PUs* contain *conservation features* whose *conservation targets* are not yet met). For local SCP in the ATLAS case studies, a decision was made to “lock in” those *PUs* which overlap or intersect with existing MPAs (Natura 2000 sites, Marine Reserves, UNESCO World Heritage Sites, etc.) as listed by the Marine Protection Atlas (<https://mpatlas.org/>), as well as existing fisheries closures (both national and international) which were considered to fall under the category of OECMs as defined by the CBD: “a geographically defined area other than a Protected Area, which is governed and managed in ways that achieve positive and sustained long-term outcomes for the in situ conservation of biodiversity, with associated ecosystem functions and services and where applicable, cultural, spiritual, socio-economic, and other locally relevant values” (CBD,2018). One notable exception to this was the decision not to “lock in” the area below the 800m depth contour which is now protected by the recent EU regulation 2016/2336 of the European Parliament (EC, 2016). This decision was made in order to avoid the major pitfall of terrestrial conservation efforts noted by Margules and Pressey (2000) – i.e. disproportionately protecting areas which contain an unrepresentative sample of biodiversity. The vast majority of area protected by EU regulation 2016/2336 is comparatively homogenous (comprising largely abyssal muds and sands) and thus not representative of the diversity of marine habitats present in EU waters.

The *PU* grid can comprise any arrangement of discrete spatial units or cells, which may be regular in shape (e.g. a tessellation of triangles, squares, or hexagons), or irregular (e.g. based on existing features such as property boundaries or catchment areas etc.). Hexagonal grids,

however, have many benefits over other regular grids; being the closest approximation of a circle which can be used to form a regular tessellating pattern, 1) the distance from the centre of each hexagonal *PU* to the centre of its 6 hexagonal neighbours is equal, 2) they offer the lowest possible perimeter to area ratio thereby minimizing boundary effects (described in more detail later in this text) (Ardron et al., 2010), and 3) they can better fit a curved surface, which can be particularly important in large marine planning areas where the curvature of the earth may be a non-trivial consideration. Hexagonal grids also provide aesthetic benefits in that they can better conform to the curved boundaries evident in natural marine structures such as coastlines, continental slopes, reefs, and seamounts etc., and this can result in MPA selections whose perimeters appear more natural/organic.

2.5.1.2.5. Cost

Systematic conservation planning is used to identify sets of areas that meet *conservation targets* for a minimal *cost*, but is important to understand that, while this can be a socio-economic cost (such as potential revenue losses associated with prohibiting fishing in a given area), the *cost* need not necessarily be a monetary one. A simple example would be the case of the “minimum set problem” for which Marxan was originally designed to solve (Ball and Possingham, 2000): here the objective is to identify the sets of areas that meet *conservation targets* while covering a minimum area – i.e. the area of the reserve is the *cost* in this instance. Each planning unit has a *cost* associated with it, and the sum of the *cost* of all *PU*s selected in an SCP solution is the primary contributor to the *cost* of the solution as a whole. The second parameter which has an effect on the *cost* of the solution is the external perimeter of the MPA network, i.e. the sum of the lengths of the external edges of *PU*s selected in the solution. The importance of this parameter can be increased by selecting a larger “boundary length modifier” (BLM) which will result in a more “clumped” solution at the expense of covering a greater area, and vice-versa by reducing the BLM to achieve a more fragmented solution which will cover a smaller area but at the expense of having more external boundaries associated with many smaller isolated MPAs. Setting the BLM to 0 will ignore the effect of perimeter entirely resulting in a solution which achieves *conservation targets* for a truly minimal area, while setting the BLM to a value such that it is of much greater importance than the *cost* associated with selecting a *PU* could potentially result in all *PU*s in the *PA* being selected to form a single large MPA– i.e. a solution which meets the *conservation target* while having a minimum perimeter. Naturally, neither of these cases is desirable, and best practice is to select a BLM such that the perimeter *cost* and the *PU cost* are of a similar order of magnitude (Ardron et al., 2010); all SCP solutions in this deliverable are the result of using a BLM of 1, with perimeter measured in units of km (as area was measured in units of km²).

In this SCP exercise, the use of four distinct *cost* parameters was explored; taking α to be the area of a single *PU* in km², the *PU costs* in each of the four cases (and the reasoning in choosing these *costs*) were as follows:

A) PU area [min *cost*: α ; max *cost*: α];

Using *cost* “A” would result in selection of a solution MPA network of minimal area for the given BLM of 1.

B) As for A but with an additional CEA penalty of up to 100% the areal *cost* (see ATLAS Milestone Report 30) [min *cost*: α ; max *cost*: 2α];

Using *cost* “B” would also result in selection of a solution MPA network of minimal area for the given BLM of 1, but subject to two constraints: 1) Fishing activity would be avoided to the greatest degree possible thereby minimizing the socioeconomic trade-offs required to operationalise the solution MPA network, and 2) where the selection of *PU*s containing habitats subject to fishing activity is unavoidable to achieving a viable SCP solution, conservation of habitats that are least impacted (i.e. closest to pristine) will be prioritized over habitats which are already significantly degraded.

C) As for B but with an additional climate change penalty of up to 100% the areal *cost* (based on the predicted reductions in biodiversity predicted in ATLAS Deliverable 3.2) [min *cost*: α ; max *cost*: 3α];

Using *cost* “C” would also result in selection of a solution MPA network of minimal area for the given BLM of 1, but subject to a third constraint (i.e. in addition to the two constraints described above): habitats that are predicted to be comparatively least impacted by the effects of climate will be prioritized for conservation of over habitats predicted to be most adversely impacted (i.e. protection will be afforded preferentially to the habitats with the best long-term viability). This was based on the degree of reduction in habitat suitability of a given *PU* when comparing current and future predicted species/habitat distributions on a scale of 0 (no change) to 1 (future absence), and was calculated on the basis of the SDM outputs of ATLAS Work Package 3.

D) As for C but with a discount of up 33% based on the basin-scale SCP exercise carried out in ATLAS deliverable 3.4 [min *cost*: 0.66α ; max *cost*: 2α];

Using *cost* “D” would also result in selection of a solution MPA network of minimal area for the given BLM of 1, but subject to a fourth constraint (i.e. in addition to the three constraints described above):

habitats which are identified to be of special importance for connectivity at the scale of the North-Atlantic basin will be given priority for protection. This was achieved by analysing solutions produced in ATLAS Deliverable 3.4 and Combes et al. (in review) and “discounting” *PU*s relative to the selection frequency of the larger basin-scale *PU*s overlying them; a maximum “discount” of 33% was applied to local-scale *PU*s which were within larger basin-scale *PU*s selected in all of the basin-scale SCP runs.

For this ATLAS deliverable, twelve “baseline” SCP scenarios were investigated for each ATLAS Case Study areas. These scenarios were the *conservation problems* obtained by considering the various combinations of *conservation targets* and *PU costs* as summarised in Figure 2.10, below, while “locking in” *PU*s which intersect or overlap with existing MPAs in the *PA*.

Cost	Conservation Target (Applied Uniformly to ALL features)		
	10%	30%	50%
A) Area Of Planning Units	Scenario 1	Scenario 5	Scenario 9
B) As above + CEA <i>Penalty</i> (0-100%)	Scenario 2	Scenario 6	Scenario 10
C) As above + Climate Change <i>Penalty</i> (0-100%)	Scenario 3	Scenario 7	Scenario 11
D) As above + Basin-Scale Importance <i>Discount</i> (0-33%)	Scenario 4	Scenario 8	Scenario 12

Table 2. 4. “Baseline” SCP scenarios investigated for this ATLAS deliverable.

In addition to investigating these “baseline” scenarios, additional scenarios were explored as illustrative examples in some of the Case Studies, such as a scenario investigating the application of the CBD’s 2030 targets; this was achieved by “locking in” the 10% scenario obtained in Scenario 4 (as defined above) and (using the same PU cost “D”) then expanding the MPA network to a minimum conservation target of 30% for all conservation features, up to 60% for “*areas of particular importance for biodiversity*”, which were taken to be the ICES VME habitats and the OSPAR threatened and declining habitats as described above.

2.5.1.2.6. SCP operations

In summary, the *prioritizr* R package uses integer linear programming (ILP) techniques to identify the area which most efficiently meets a given **conservation target** by minimizing the value of a **cost** function. The **cost** function is primarily based on the sum of the **costs** of the set of **PU**s selected to meet the given **conservation targets**, but it also considers the total perimeter of the identified network in order to favour contiguous closures over a scattered network of smaller unconnected closures. While solutions fitting the latter description would likely comprise a smaller area, such disjointed networks would be suboptimal, not just in terms of biological connectivity, but because it would not be practicable to enforce such a fragmented network of closures. The identified solution, then, is a minimum **cost** solution, not in absolute terms of the sum of the **costs** of the **PU**s selected for conservation, but a minimal **cost** solution subject to the constraint that the contiguity of the identified solution must also be within certain reasonable bounds.

While *prioritizr* does have the ability to identify an “optimal” conservation solution, it is important to remember that the software is a decision support tool and not a decision making tool; the solutions produced by the software are made solely on the basis of the (often limited) data input it receives. For these reasons, it is desirable (and often necessary) that marine planners have access to a portfolio of solutions to allow them sufficient flexibility to make nuanced decisions which take account of information not readily considered by SCP software (e.g. political considerations etc.). To provide this flexibility, each **conservation problem** was solved 100 times to create a portfolio of solutions whose cost was within 30% of the theoretically optimal solution. The selection frequency of the **PU**s across 100 *prioritizr* solutions is represented in the output figures by the opacity of the cells comprising the planning unit grid; **PU**s selected in all 100 *prioritizr* runs are completely opaque, while **PU**s not selected in any *prioritizr* runs are completely transparent. This selection frequency is similarly reflected by the bars on the charts accompanying the SCP solutions, and results in their “fading out” gradually as they reach higher percentages of feature cover – this indicates that **PU**s protecting some of a features range were not selected in all 100 runs, and depending on the threshold used to define a closure network (e.g. including all cells selected in >70% of runs), varying proportions of a **conservation feature** will be protected. Figure 2.13, below, provides a “key” to interpreting these output figures.

Figure 2.13. Key to interpreting SCP output maps.

Due to the immense size and complexity of the *conservation problems* developed for the ATLAS Case Studies, it was extremely computationally intensive to identify optimal solutions. To overcome this, the Work Package 6 project team linked with the Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC) to run *prioritizr* using Kay, Ireland's national supercomputer for academic researchers. Computation of SCP solutions was delegated one of Kay's 336 nodes, each of which comprises 2x 20-core 2.4 GHz Intel Xeon Gold 6148 (Skylake) processors, 192 GiB of RAM, a 400 GiB local SSD for scratch space and a 100Gbit OmniPath network adaptor; by using the Gurobi (v9.1) Mathematical Optimization Solver, it was possible to fully leverage Kay's computational power via parallel computation of SCP solutions using all 40 available cores on any given node.

2.5.1.3. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features by area

Figure 2. 14. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 1 (10% target) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The SCP Scenario 1 solution exceeds 10% protection for all conservation features by extending existing SACs and adding some new areas, e.g. the South-West Deeps.

2.5.1.4. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features while minimizing the impact on current fishing activities

Figure 2. 15. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 2 (10% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The goal here is to reach the conservation target of 10% while minimising the impact on current fishing activities. This leads to a degree of fragmentation, reduction in size of the extensions out from existing SACs, e.g. the Hovland Mounds and the removal of the South-West Deeps (Figure 2. 15).

2.5.1.5. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features while minimizing the impact on current fishing activities, taking into account climate change effects and the importance of the SDM at basin scale for conservation.

The third planning scenario determines the minimum area needed to meet a conservation target of 10% for ALL conservation features WHILE minimizing the impact on current fishing activity AND accounting for future climate change effects and considering the importance of the Porcupine SMA at the basin scale (Figure 3.34). Each planning unit, in addition to the areal and cumulative impacts costs described in 2.5.1.3 above, was assigned a further ‘climate change’ cost based on the degree of reduction in habitat suitability of a given cell when comparing current and future predicted species/habitat distributions on a scale of 0

(no change) to 1 (future absence). The importance of conservation actions in the Porcupine at basin level were also considered by assigning a value on a scale of 0 (no importance) to 1 (high importance) with reference to the basin scale systematic conservation planning solutions produced in Atlas Deliverable 3.4 and Combes et al. (in review). The final cost of a planning unit was discounted up to a maximum of 33%.

Figure 2. 16. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 4 (10% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%, climate change penalty of 0-100% and basin scale importance discount of 0-25%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The solution here picks out some deeper areas (e.g. south of the Belgica Mounds) and new areas to the north of the Porcupine Bank.

Overlaying current fishing activity on the Scenario 4 solution (Figure 2.17) shows that the planning algorithm has done a good job of finding solutions that minimise disruption to fishing. Only the areas selected on the plateau and west of Flemish Pass/Eastern Canyon could result in a requirement for some displacement of fishing effort.

Figure 2.17. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 4 (Figure 2.13) with current fishing activity overlain.

2.6. Evaluation of management effectiveness and recommend adaption to current management in the light of climate change (MESMA Steps 6 and 7).

2.6.1. Expanded MPA network and climate change

2.6.1.1. Expanded MPA network to meet 30% area target and climate change

The UN Convention of Biological Diversity (CDB) Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework sets out an ambitious plan to implement broad-based action to bring about a transformation in society’s relationship with biodiversity and to ensure that, by 2050, the shared vision of living in harmony with nature is fulfilled. The framework is intended to contribute to the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

While the UN Sustainable Development Goal 14, Aichi Target 1, calls for 10% Marine Protected Area coverage globally by 2020, negotiations are underway to set new targets for adoption in the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework⁹. The International Union for Conservation Network (IUCN) membership have approved a new global target for MPAs of

⁹ www.cbd.int/article/zero-draft-update-august-2020

setting aside “30% of each marine habitat” in “highly protected MPAs and other effective area-based conservation measures” by 2030. Although the 30%-by-2030 target is not binding on nations, the European Union has already embraced it as a goal in its recently published EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Report¹⁰.

To test what a 30% by 2030 conservation target might look like for the Porcupine SMA we ran a systematic conservation planning exercise for a CBD 2030 scenario which used the same costs (area, cumulative impacts and climate change effects) and basin scale importance discounts as applied in Scenario 4 in 2.5.1.4 above, but with a 30% rather than a 10% conservation target, and “locking in” the previous 10% solution as a starting point, rather than just using the existing fisheries closures network. The resulting conservation solution is presented in Figure 2.18. The 30% solution with the configuration of costs and penalties used here, identifies seafloor to the northwest of Ireland and abyssal seafloor to the southwest.

Figure 2.18. The degree of protection offered under SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (30% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%, climate change penalty of 0-100% and basin scale importance discount of 0-25%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

¹⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/strategy/index_en.htm

Figure 2.19. The SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (Figure 2.18) overlain with current fishing activity.

Even with the 30% conservation target reached for all conservation features, the algorithm is able to avoid most of the main fishing grounds (Figure 2.19).

2.6.2. Oil and gas exploration and climate change

Overlaying current oil and gas concessions on the CBD 2030 conservation solution (2.18) for the Irish offshore shows some potential for interaction, for example, in the Celtic Sea. However, given the Irish Government's intention to phase out oil and gas activities it's unlikely that the sector will hinder the future expansion of conservation management actions required to meet evolving international obligations.

Figure 2.20. SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (Figure 2.12) with an overlay of current oil and gas exploration, significant discovery and production licence blocks.

2.7. Governance (MESMA Step 8)

2.7.1. The role of Systematic Conservation Planning in Maritime Spatial Planning

Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) serve not only to conserve biodiversity, but to improve the welfare of society as a whole by safeguarding the tangible and intangible goods and services provided by marine ecosystems. The European Green Deal and the recently published EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030 place a strong emphasis on the importance of biodiversity for human wellbeing and development, with the latter calling for 30% of marine areas to be effectively managed protected areas in conjunction with existing Natura 2000 initiatives by the year 2030. This sentiment echoes the ambitions laid out in other national and international strategies, perhaps most notably the Convention on Biological Diversity's (CBD) Post-2020 Biodiversity Framework, which outlines the need to protect at least 30% of land and sea areas

(with at least 10% under strict protection) and 60% of “*sites of particular importance for biodiversity*” through protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures (OECMs) (CBD, 2020). This Post-2020 Framework intends to build on the Aichi Targets laid out in the CBD’s Strategic Plan for Biodiversity, 2011-2020, most specifically Target 11, which proposed that by 2020 “*10 per cent of coastal and marine areas, especially areas of particular importance for biodiversity and ecosystem services, would be conserved through effectively and equitably managed, ecologically representative and well connected systems of protected areas and OECMs*” .

In achieving these conservation objectives, the definitions of what specifically constitutes an MPA or an OECM is obviously of critical importance, and these definitions must be robust enough that conservation initiatives not fall foul of ‘target gaming’ by national governments (Humphreys and Clark, 2020) – i.e. “hitting the target but missing the point” (Hood, 2006). Unfortunately, compelling arguments have been made that this may in fact already be happening (Claudet et al., 2020; Humphreys and Clark, 2020; Sala et al., 2018), and conservation of marine biodiversity may be following the precedent set by terrestrial biodiversity conservation efforts, where protected area networks on land – often located in remote regions where human influences on the environment are already minimal – have long been noted to contain an unrepresentative sample of biodiversity (Margules and Pressey, 2000). Many remote areas afforded “protection” by government legislation are in effect already protected by virtue of their inaccessibility and are thus unlikely to be impacted by human pressures. Therefore, any official designations to declare such areas as “protected” serves to provide the least possible protection to biodiversity; this is already becoming evident in nations’ responses to the meeting of marine conservation objectives, where it has been argued that the focus appears to be achieving quantity over quality (manifesting as a rush to establish large and remote MPAs) which may ultimately be detrimental to the cause of conservation of biodiversity (Giglio et al., 2018).

It is clear then, that to achieve meaningful conservation objectives, protected areas must be selectively located and effectively managed (Woodley et al., 2019). Systematic conservation planning (SCP) presents a promising solution to this problem, offering an objective, quantitative, and transparent process by which to identify areas that meet certain conservation objectives (specifically such as those outlined by the CBD (Kockel et al., 2020)) while satisfying various criteria such as expanding on existing protected area networks (EC, 2020) and avoiding unnecessarily disruptive and contentious socioeconomic trade-offs (Worm et al., 2009).

2.7.2. Future Proofing Conservation Requirements

The draft Irish National Marine Planning Framework and the Marine Planning and Development Management Bill should account for the future requirements to increase areas under conservation management. Looking beyond 2030, some scientists are already calling for 50% of the oceans to be protected by 2050. What that might look like in the Irish offshore is shown in Fig. x below. Putting in place a zoning system similar to green belts in terrestrial planning, i.e. ‘blue’ belts, where potential developments have to meet more stringent licensing requirements to proceed would ensure that Ireland can more easily meet its future international conservation commitments.

Figure 2.21. The degree of protection offered under a potential CBD 2050 Scenario (50% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%, climate change penalty of 0-100% and basin scale importance discount of 0-25%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

2.8. References

- Ardron, J.A., Possingham, H.P., Klein, C.J., 2010. Marxan good practices handbook, Version 2. Pac. Mar. Anal. Res. Assoc. Vic. BC Can. 165.
- Ball, I.R., Possingham, H.P., 2000. MARXAN (V1. 8.2). Mar. Reserve Des. Using Spatially Explic. Annealing Man.
- Bas, T.L., 2010. Human Activities on the Deep Seafloor in the North East Atlantic: An Assessment of Spatial Extent. PLOS ONE 5, e12730. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0012730>
- Callery, O., Grehan, A. Stirling, D. 2020. Mapping the Cumulative Impact of Bottom Fisheries on Benthic Habitats in 12 ATLAS Case Study Areas. Atlas Milestone Report 30.
- CBD. 2011. Aichi Target 11. Decision X/2. Convention on Biological Diversity.
- CBD. 2018. Decision Adopted by the Conference of the Parties to the Convention on Biological Diversity 14/8. Protected areas and other effective area-based conservation measures. CBD/ COP/DEC/14/8. 30 November 2018.
- CBD. 2020. Zero Draft of the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework <https://www.cbd.int/article/2020-01-10-19-02-38>.
- Claudet, J., Loiseau, C., Sostres, M., Zupan, M., 2020. Underprotected Marine Protected Areas in a Global Biodiversity Hotspot. One Earth 2, 380–384. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oneear.2020.03.008>
- Daigle, R.M., Metaxas, A., Balbar, A.C., McGowan, J., Trembl, E.A., Kuempel, C.D., Possingham, H.P., Beger, M., 2020. Operationalizing ecological connectivity in spatial conservation planning with Marxan Connect. Methods Ecol. Evol. 11, 570–579.
- Dorschel, B., AJ Wheeler, X Monteys, K Verbruggen (2010). Porcupine Seabight. Atlas of the Deep-Water Seabed: Ireland, 129-131pp.

- Ekeboom, J., Jäänheimo, J., Reker, J., Kindström, M., Lindblad, C., Mattisson, A., Sandström, A., Jermakovs, V., 2008. Towards marine spatial planning in the Baltic Sea. BALANCE Tech. Summ. Rep. 4.
- European Commission. (2016). Council Directive 2016/2336 on establishing specific conditions for fishing for deep-sea stocks in the north-east Atlantic and provisions for fishing in international waters of the north-east Atlantic and repealing Council Regulation 2347/2002.
- European Commission. 2020 Communication from the commission to the European parliament, the council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions: EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030. Bringing nature back into our lives.
- Evans, J.L., Peckett, F., Howell, K.L., 2015. Combined application of biophysical habitat mapping and systematic conservation planning to assess efficiency and representativeness of the existing High Seas MPA network in the Northeast Atlantic. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* 72, 1483–1497. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsv012>
- Garson, J., Aggarwal, A., Sarkar, S., 2002. Resnet manual. Biodivers. Biocultural Conserv. Lab. Sect. Integr. Biol. Univ. Tex. Austin.
- Giglio, V.J., Pinheiro, H.T., Bender, M.G., Bonaldo, R.M., Costa-Lotufu, L.V., Ferreira, C.E.L., Floeter, S.R., Freire, A., Gasparini, J.L., Joyeux, J.-C., Krajewski, J.P., Lindner, A., Longo, G.O., Lotufu, T.M.C., Loyola, R., Luiz, O.J., Macieira, R.M., Magris, R.A., Mello, T.J., Quimbayo, J.P., Rocha, L.A., Segal, B., Teixeira, J.B., Vila-Nova, D.A., Vilar, C.C., Zilberberg, C., Francini-Filho, R.B., 2018. Large and remote marine protected areas in the South Atlantic Ocean are flawed and raise concerns: Comments on Soares and Lucas (2018). *Mar. Policy* 96, 13–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.07.017>
- Grehan, A., Unnithan, V., Wheeler, A., Monteys, X., Beck, T., Wilson, M., Guinan, J., Hall-Spencer, J.M., Foubert, A., Klages, M., 2004. Evidence of major fisheries impact on cold-water corals in the deep-waters off the Porcupine Bank, west coast of Ireland: are interim management measures required, in: *ICES Annual Science Symp.*, Vigo, Spain.
- Hanson, J., Schuster, R., Morrell, N., Strimas-Mackey, M., Watts, M.E., Arcese, P., Possingham, H.P., 2017. prioritizr: systematic conservation prioritization in R. R Packag. 10 10 Ed.
- Hood, C., 2006. Gaming in Targetworld: The Targets Approach to Managing British Public Services. *Public Adm. Rev.* 66, 515–521.
- Howell, K.L., 2010. A benthic classification system to aid in the implementation of marine protected area networks in the deep/high seas of the NE Atlantic. *Biol. Conserv.* 143, 1041–1056. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2010.02.001>
- Humphreys, J., Clark, R.W.E., 2020. Chapter 1 - A critical history of marine protected areas, in: Humphreys, J., Clark, R.W.E. (Eds.), *Marine Protected Areas*. Elsevier, pp. 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102698-4.00001-0>
- ICES. 2019. Stakeholder workshop to disseminate the ICES deep-sea access regulation technical service, and scope the required steps for regulatory purposes (WKREG). *ICES Scientific Reports*. 1:79. 34 pp.
- Kazanidis, G., Orejas, C., Borja, A., Kenchington, E., Henry, L.-A., Callery, O., Carreiro-Silva, M., Egilsdottir, H., Giacomello, E., Grehan, A., Menot, L., Morato, T., Ragnarsson, S.Á., Rueda, J.L., Stirling, D., Stratmann, T., van Oevelen, D., Palialexis, A., Johnson, D., Roberts, J.M., 2020. Assessing the environmental status of selected North Atlantic deep-sea ecosystems. *Ecol. Indic.* 119, 106624. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2020.106624>
- Keppel, G., Wardell-Johnson, G.W., 2012. Refugia: keys to climate change management. *Glob. Change Biol.* 18, 2389–2391. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2486.2012.02729.x>
- Kockel, A., Ban, N.C., Costa, M., Dearden, P., 2020. Evaluating approaches for scaling-up community-based marine-protected areas into socially equitable and ecologically representative networks. *Conserv. Biol.* 34, 137–147. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13368>
- Margules, C.R., Pressey, R.L., 2000. Systematic conservation planning. *Nature* 405, 243–253. <https://doi.org/10.1038/35012251>
- Moilanen, A., Kujala, H., Leathwick, J.R., 2009. The Zonation framework and software for conservation prioritization. *Spat. Conserv. Prioritization* 135, 196–210.
- MPAAG (2020). Expanding Ireland’s Marine Protected Area Network: A report by the Marine Protected Area Advisory Group. Report for the Department of Housing, Local Government and Heritage, Ireland.
- Orejas, C., Kenchington, E., Rice, J., Kazanidis, G., Palialexis, A., Johnson, D., Gianni, M., Danovaro, R., Roberts, J.M., 2020. Towards a common approach to the assessment of the environmental status of deep-sea ecosystems in areas beyond national jurisdiction. *Mar. Policy* 104182. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.104182>
- Populus, J., Vasquez, M., Albrecht, J., Manca, E., Agnesi, S., Al Hamdani, Z., Andersen, J., Annunziatellis, A., Bekkby, T., Bruschi, A., 2017. EUSeaMap. A European broad-scale seabed habitat map.
- Pouzols, F.M., Moilanen, A., 2013. RobOff: software for analysis of alternative land-use options and conservation actions. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 4, 426–432. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12040>

- Pressey, R.L., Watts, M.E., Barrett, T.W., Ridges, M.J., 2009. The C-Plan conservation planning system: origins, applications, and possible futures. *Spat. Conserv. Prioritization Quant. Methods Comput. Tools* 211–34.
- Sala, E., Lubchenco, J., Grorud-Colvert, K., Novelli, C., Roberts, C., Sumaila, U.R., 2018. Assessing real progress towards effective ocean protection. *Mar. Policy* 91, 11–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.02.004>
- Sarkar, S., Fuller, T., Aggarwal, A., Moffett, A., Kelley, C.D., 2009. 16. The ConsNet Software Platform for Systematic Conservation Planning.
- Schmiing, M., Diogo, H., Serrão Santos, R., Afonso, P., 2015. Marine conservation of multispecies and multi-use areas with various conservation objectives and targets. *ICES J. Mar. Sci.* 72, 851–862. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icesjms/fsu180>
- Schuster, R., Hanson, J.O., Strimas-Mackey, M., Bennett, J.R., 2020. Exact integer linear programming solvers outperform simulated annealing for solving conservation planning problems. *PeerJ* 8. <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9258>
- Watts, M.E., Ball, I.R., Stewart, R.S., Klein, C.J., Wilson, K., Steinback, C., Lourival, R., Kircher, L., Possingham, H.P., 2009. Marxan with Zones: Software for optimal conservation based land-and sea-use zoning. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 24, 1513–1521.
- Woodley, S., Locke, H., Laffoley, D., MacKinnon, K., Sandwith, T., Smart, J., 2019. A Review of Evidence for Area-based Conservation Targets for the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework. *PARKS Int. J. Prot. Areas Conserv.* 25, 31–46.
- Worm, B., Hilborn, R., Baum, J.K., Branch, T.A., Collie, J.S., Costello, C., Fogarty, M.J., Fulton, E.A., Hutchings, J.A., Jennings, S., Jensen, O.P., Lotze, H.K., Mace, P.M., McClanahan, T.R., Minto, C., Palumbi, S.R., Parma, A.M., Ricard, D., Rosenberg, A.A., Watson, R., Zeller, D., 2009. Rebuilding Global Fisheries. *Science* 325, 578–585. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1173146>

3. Flemish Cap Case Study

3.1. Context Setting

3.1.1. Set boundaries for Spatial Managed Area (SMA) Assessment (MESMA 1a)

3.1.1.1. Description of the Case Study Area

The study area comprises both the Flemish Cap and the Flemish Pass area. It is located in the high seas (ABNJ) within the NAFO Regulatory Area (NRA) (NAFO Divs. 3LM), with the seafloor within the extended continental shelf of the coastal state (Figure 3. 22). The size of the case study area is about 124,000 km². Flemish Cap is an Oceanic Bank located about 600 km to the east of Newfoundland and separated from the Grand Banks of Newfoundland by a rift zone known as Flemish Pass, at depths which may reach 1,200 m. The Bank (a plateau of about 200 km in radius) comprises about 48,700 km² within the bathymetric contours of 200 m depth (depths range between 125 m and 1,500 m).

Figure 3. 22. Map of the southern part of the NAFO Regulatory Area (NRA) showing the location of the case study. The NRA is located in the high seas, with part of the seafloor within the extended continental shelf of the coastal state.

The study area includes several types of valuable habitats and ecosystems (e.g. cold-water corals and deep sea sponges, see Kenchington *et al.*, 2014) and several types of existing and potential human activities (Table 3. 5). Currently, the main human activities in the region are fisheries, shipping, undersea cable routes, scientific research and offshore hydrocarbon exploration. There is potential for increased offshore oil and gas exploration leading to exploitation in the area (NAFO, 2019a). However, this will present a potential conflict for: (i)

existing activities (e.g. High Seas fisheries), (ii) management measures such as areas closed to bottom fishing (NAFO, 2020) and (iii) VMEs identified by NAFO.

Table 3. 5. Preliminary list of existing and potential human activities identified in the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass area.

Sector/Driver	Subsector	Activity
Fisheries	Bottom fisheries	Pots, traps, gillnets, trawls and longlines
	Pelagic fisheries	Seines, gillnets, trawls and longlines
Exploitation and exploration of non-living resources and ocean energy	Offshore oil and gas	Exploration (drilling and seismic activities)
		Exploitation (significant discoveries/production)
		Pipelines
	Offshore renewables	Wind, tidal and current energy converters
		Power cables
	Mining	Seabed mining
Carbon capture and storage	Carbon capture and storage	
Transportation	Shipping	Shipping (passengers and items)
Telecommunication	Undersea cables	Laying and maintain undersea cables
Science	Research and education	Fish stock assessment and ecosystem surveys
Conservation	Environmental conservation and protection	Environmental conservation and protection (including VMEs)
Biotechnology	Bioprospecting	Search for biological compounds and genetic resources
Defence	Military activities	Dumping, sonar, training
External influences	Climate change	Climate change
	Pollution	Pollution (including marine litter and long- distance pollution)

3.1.1.2. Institutional Landscape

The institutional landscape in relation to the governance of fisheries and oil and gas in the study area is summarised in

Table 3.6. There is no integrated spatial management plan in place for the study area.

However, there are ongoing independent active sectoral plans for fisheries and hydrocarbon management: (i) fisheries in the high seas are managed by NAFO, meanwhile (ii) offshore oil and gas resources activities in the Canadian extended continental shelf are managed by the Canada-Newfoundland and Labrador Offshore Petroleum Board (C-NLOPB). Environmental assessments (EAs) of offshore oil and gas projects are managed under C-NLOPB (“project-based” EAs under the *Accord Acts*) or under the Impact Assessment Agency of Canada – IAAC (“designated projects” EA, under the former *Canadian Environmental Assessment Act – CEAA 2012*, or the new *Impact Assessment Act – IAA 2019*).

Table 3.6. Summary of the institutional landscape in the Case Study area regarding High Seas fisheries and offshore oil and gas.

Sector	Fisheries (NAFO Stocks)	Offshore oil and gas (exploration and exploitation)
Management authority	NAFO	C-NLOPB ² / IAAC ³ former CEAA
Zoning and jurisdiction	High seas (international water column)	Extended continental shelf (seabed and subsoil)
Spatial boundary	NAFO Regulatory Area	Eastern Newfoundland and Labrador offshore Area
Operational level	Intergovernmental, international (12 Contracting Parties): NAFO (Regional Fisheries Management Organization).	Coastal State: C-NLOPB (Board); IAAC (Agency)
MSP relevant objectives	NAFO: Long term conservation and sustainable use of the fishery resources and to safeguard the marine ecosystems	C-NLOPB: To facilitate the exploration for and development of the petroleum resources, including safety, environmental protection, resource management and industrial benefits. IAAC: impact assessment process.
MSP relevant management instruments	NAFO Conservation and Enforcement Measures, including bottom fishing closures to protect VMEs; NAFO Road Map to Ecosystem Approach Framework.	C-NLOPB management mandate under the <i>Accord Acts</i> ; Licences and authorizations; Strategic Environmental Assessments (SEA); Regional Assessment under IAAC; Environmental Assessments (EAs): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Project-based” EAs under the <i>Accords Acts</i> • “Designated projects” EAs under <i>Federal laws</i>

3.1.1.3. Flemish Cap Spatial Managed Area

The spatial managed area for the Flemish Cap Case Study corresponds to the area identified as an Ecologically or Biologically Significant Marine Area (EBSA) in UNEP (2014): Area No. 4 - Slopes of the Flemish Cap and Grand Banks (Figure 3. 22). This area holds most of the vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs) found in international waters within the NAFO Regulatory Area including all the VME closed areas to protect corals and sponges, the fishing footprint, the area covered by a current NAFO management plan and most of the areas of interest for hydrocarbon exploration, shipping, research, cables, etc.

3.1.2. Define goals and operational objectives for the SMA (MESMA 1b)

3.1.2.1. Blue Growth Goals

The blue growth goal is to ensure potential oil and gas extraction causes minimum disruption of existing activities (e.g. high seas fisheries) and for the delivery of ecosystem goods and services (e.g. fish stocks, vulnerable habitats and ecosystems, etc.), including protection of cold- water corals and deep-sea sponges.

3.1.2.2. Operational Objectives

- Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity in support of the conservation measures in the NAFO management plan.
- Maintain current fisheries at or close to MSY taking into account wider ecosystem impacts.
- Assess the potential impacts of oil and gas developments.

3.2.2. Collate and map existing information

3.2.1. Identify ecosystem components (MESMA 2a) and human activities, pressures and impacts (MESMA 2b)

All relevant biophysical (Figure 3.23) and socio-economic (Figure 3.24) components of the ecosystem were mapped, taking into account the importance of such components and the availability of data in the SMA. All this information was organized and integrated into a GIS using the open source software QGIS (v3.4) which allows maps to be easily updated when additional information becomes available.

Figure 3.23. Preliminary mapping of natural components of the ecosystem in ATLAS Case Study No11 (Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass) from several available sources (NEREIDA, IEO, Thesis FJM [USC-IEO], NAFO, OBIS, etc.). QGIS Geographic Information System.

Figure 3.24. Mapping of socio-economic components of the ecosystem (human activities) in ATLAS Case Study No11 (Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass) from several sources (IEO, NAFO, DFO, García-Alegre et al., 2020, C-NLOPB, OBIS, etc.).

3.2.2. Identify existing management measures (MESMA 2c)

A number of fisheries closures have been established to protect vulnerable marine habitats in the Flemish Cap (Figure 3.25). Those that occur in the Flemish Cap SMA (whole or in part) are listed in

Table 3.7, together with area protected which ranges from as little as 35km² in the Northwest Flemish Cap Area to a maximum of 2883km² in the Northeast Flemish Cap Area. In total an area of 9121km² is protected within the boundary of the SMA. The total area of the SMA, by comparison, is 124903km² which means that ~ 7.3% of the SMA is closed to bottom trawling at present.

Figure 3.25. Current NAFO fisheries closures protecting Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (VME) in the Flemish Cap SME.

Name	Area (km ²)
Flemish Pass / Eastern Canyon	2686
Eastern Flemish Cap	1359
Northeast Flemish Cap	2883
Sackville Spur	959
Northern Flemish Cap Area 1	258
Northern Flemish Cap Area 2	98
Northern Flemish Cap Area 3	128
Northwest Flemish Cap Area 1	315
Northwest Flemish Cap Area 2	61
Northwest Flemish Cap Area 3	35
Beothuk Knoll	339
TOTAL	9121

Table 3.7. List of fisheries closures within the Flemish Cap SMA.

3.3. Select indicators and benchmarks (MESMA Step 3)

3.3.1. Seabed litter

Marine litter has been recognized as a worldwide problem affecting the marine environment in several ways: economic loss, degradation of habitats and impact on biota. Marine litter is distributed throughout the marine environment (coastal areas, water column and seabed). Despite an important increase in the number of studies on marine litter in recent years, there are still gaps in the knowledge, especially related to the high-seas and deep waters. To address the concerns about seabed litter in NAFO Regulatory Area, a pilot study (García-Alegre *et al.*, 2020) was conducted by the IEO-Vigo, under ATLAS Project, analysing an extensive database based on EU-Spain groundfish surveys (Durán Muñoz *et al.*, 2020a) in Div. 3L. This study shows a low occurrence and density of seabed litter in the Flemish Pass, Div. 3L (Table 3. 5), for which NAFO-managed and non-NAFO managed fisheries are the primary sources (Figure 3.26, Figure 3.27, Figure 3.28). In most cases, litter consisted of small fragments of rope but in some, litter consisted of entire traps or nets (Figure 3.26). The highest densities of seabed litter were found in the deepest areas located in the Flemish Pass channel and down the north-eastern flank of the Grand Bank.

Table 3.8. Mean values of marine litter densities estimated by kg/km² and number of items/km² by year and in the total period (N, number of valid trawls performed; %, percentage of valid trawls with litter presence). Flemish Pass, Div. 3L. Source: García-Alegre *et al.* 2020.

Year	N	%	kg/km ²	Item/km ²
2006	100	19	3.8 ± 2.1	4.1 ± 1
2007	94	17	97.6 ± 63.5	3.1 ± 0.9
2008	100	7.0	1.9 ± 1.1	1.4 ± 0.6
2009	98	6.1	0.4 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.3
2010	97	4.1	0.2 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.4
2011	89	3.4	0.9 ± 0.8	0.6 ± 0.3
2012	98	8.2	8.1 ± 5.9	1.3 ± 0.5
2013	100	4.0	3.5 ± 2.4	0.9 ± 0.5
2014	99	5.1	6.7 ± 4.2	0.9 ± 0.5
2015	97	5.2	1.1 ± 0.6	0.6 ± 0.3
2016	98	12.2	4.5 ± 2.2	1.5 ± 0.4
2017	99	8.1	1.9 ± 1.1	1.2 ± 0.4
2006-2017	1169	8.3	10.6 ± 5.2	1.4 ± 0.4

This pioneering study is relevant to improve our knowledge on MSFD Descriptor 10 in the deep-sea and ABJN. It is worth noting that based on this study, NAFO WG-ESA recommended to the Scientific Council that standardized protocols for marine litter data collection should be implemented by all Contracting Parties as part of their groundfish surveys conducted in NAFO Regulatory Area (NAFO, 2019a). Implementation of such protocols would allow monitoring of the spatial and temporal distribution of marine litter,

contributing to improved knowledge of their characteristics in the NRA. Seabed litter studies contribute to the current knowledge on Good Environmental State (GES) of deep-sea ecosystems in Div. 3L, being useful to GES monitoring regarding predictions and future scenarios.

Figure 3.26. Several examples of seabed litter items found in the Flemish Pass, Div. 3L. (A-D) Abandoned, Lost or otherwise Discarded Fishing Gears (ALDFG) items. A and B (nets found in two trawl hauls in 2007 with weight of 400 kg and 250 respectively), C (trap), E (mustard pot), F (tire). Photos from García-Alegre et al., 2020.

Figure 3.27. Percentage of the occurrence of the different litter categories by trawls with litter presence. Flemish Pass, Div. 3L. Source: García-Alegre et al., 2020.

Figure 3.28. Distribution of fisheries related seabed litter items (ALDFG) found in the Flemish Pass area (NAFO Div. 3L) showing in blue scale the NAFO fishing effort (2008-2014) and in green the snow crab fishery footprint (2007-2017) (blue triangles, nets; green squares, traps; black dots, other fisheries related items). Flemish Pass, Div. 3L. Source García-Alegre et al., 2020.

3.4. Conduct risk analysis (MESMA Step 4)

3.4.1. Oil and gas risk analysis

A simple mapping of available spatial information on footprints of human activities, allowed us to identify potential user-user conflicts (e.g. hydrocarbon industry vs. deep-sea fisheries) or user-ecosystem conflicts (e.g. hydrocarbon industry vs. VMEs) in the medium term¹¹.

As an example illustrating such conflicts, the map in Figure 3.29 shows a proposed oil and gas development project in the Flemish Pass (*Bay du Nord Project*) overlapping with NAFO fisheries in Div. 3L, as well as with NAFO fisheries, VME closures and VME polygons in Div. 3M.

¹¹ "Discovered in 2013, the **Bay du Nord Project** is expected to be sanctioned in 2020, with first oil expected in 2025. With reserves of nearly 300 million barrels of oil, Bay du Nord is the first remote, deep water project in the province's offshore (500 kilometres from shore and approximately 1,200 metres deep). **It opens a new basin - the Flemish Pass ...**". Source: <https://www.gov.nl.ca/nr/energy/petroleum/offshore/projects/bay-du-nord/>

Figure 3.29. Map of the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass area (Divs. 3LM) showing the potential conflicts between different users of the marine space (e.g. oil and gas vs. fisheries) and between users and environment (oil and gas vs. VMEs). The yellow star indicates the location of the proposed production installation. Moreover, the map reveals the overlap between different regulatory frameworks (e.g. areas closed to bottom fishing are currently open to oil and gas exploration and exploitation). Sources (2018): NAFO, C-NLOPB and CBD.

The map reveals the overlap (and potential conflicts) between different management frameworks: areas closed to bottom fishing by NAFO to protect VMEs are currently open to oil and gas exploration and exploitation.

3.4.2. Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of fishing activities

The impact of multiple environmental pressures caused by demersal trawling was subjected to a cumulative environmental assessment using a workflow and decision tool developed by Callery et al. (2020). By linking the JNCC Marine Pressures Activities Database (PAD) with spatial data layers of fishing activity derived from fishing vessel automatic identification system (AIS) location data (Kroodsma et al., 2018), a map of all pressures associated with demersal trawling was compiled. A second map combining sensitivities to individual pressures for all habitats in the Flemish Cap SMA was compiled using the habitat sensitivity scores provided by the Marine Evidence-based Sensitivity Assessment (MarESA) (Callery et al. 2020), with the combination of sensitivity and pressure intensity providing a cumulative impact index for each location following the methodology developed by Halpern et al. (2008). As the sensitivity assessment is based on EUNIS habitats but the EUNIS (the European Nature Information System) classification does not as yet extend to Canada or the US, a method was developed to predict EUNIS habitats using Random Forest modelling of fish habitats and using the occurrence of fish as a habitat proxy (Callery et al. 2020). The analysis shows that a relatively high seafloor impact only occurs east of Sackville Spur

(Figure 3.30B) even though similar levels of fishing activity are recorded elsewhere (Figure 3.30A). This is due to the occurrence in the area of predicted VME and fish habitat.

Figure 3.30. A. Average hours fished per km² by all vessels identified using AIS. B. Cumulative impacts of pressures associated with bottom fishing for the Flemish Cap.

3.5. Assessment of findings against operational objectives: Blue Growth scenarios (MESMA Step 5)

3.5.1. Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of an existing or expanded network of marine protected areas while maintaining current fisheries at close to current levels.

3.5.1.1. Baseline assessment of the effectiveness of current conservation measures

Fisheries closures in the Flemish Cap SMA protect a seafloor area of 9121km² from disturbance by fishing (cf. 3.2.2). An audit was carried out to establish to what degree (% cover) the individual conservation features of interest in this study are protected. The results of a spatial analysis performed in QGIS for each feature is shown in the bar charts in Figure 3.31. The closures appear to conserve ~10% or more of individual VME habitats with the exception of the bubblegum coral, *Paragorgia arborea*, which is under-represented in the closures.

Figure 3.31. Baseline assessment of the degree of protection offered by existing conservation management measures in the Flemish Cap to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicate habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

3.5.1.2. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features by area

A systematic planning approach using the decision support tool ‘*prioritizr*’ was used to test a number of conservation scenarios in the Spatial Managed Area. The first scenario was to determine the minimum area in the Flemish Cap SMA that would be required for additional fisheries closures to meet a conservation target of 10% for ALL conservation features, i.e. VME, predicted fish, and EUNIS habitats.

The *prioritizr* R package uses integer linear programming (ILP) techniques to identify the area which most efficiently meets this 10% conservation target by minimizing the value of a “cost” function. In this scenario, the cost function is based primarily on the areal sum of the minimum set of planning units required to meet the aforementioned target, but it also considers the total perimeter of the identified network in order to favour contiguous closures over a scattered network of smaller unconnected closures. While solutions fitting the latter description would likely comprise a smaller area, such disjointed networks would be suboptimal, not just in terms of biological connectivity, but because it would not be practicable to enforce them. The identified solution then is a minimum area, not in absolute terms, but a minimal area subject to the constraint that the contiguity of the identified solution must be within certain reasonable bounds.

While *prioritizr* does have the ability to identify an “optimal” conservation solution, it is important to remember that the software is a decision support tool and not a decision making tool; the solutions produced by the software are made solely on the basis of the (often limited) data input it receives. For these reasons, it is desirable (and often necessary) that marine planners have access to a portfolio of solutions to allow them sufficient flexibility to make nuanced decisions which take account of information not readily considered by SCP software (e.g. political considerations etc.). To provide this flexibility, each conservation problem was solved 100 times to create a portfolio of solutions whose “cost” was within 30% of the theoretically optimal solution. The frequency with which individual cells are selected over 100 *prioritizr* solutions is represented in bar-charts in the figures below, as different degrees of opacity. Cells selected in all 100 *prioritizr* runs are completely opaque, while cells not selected in any *prioritizr* runs are completely transparent. The final solution consists of cells selected in 100% of the solutions as well as cells selected in less than 100% of the solutions shown by the gradual “fading out” on the bars of the chart as higher percentages of feature cover are reached. Depending on the threshold used to define a closure network (e.g. including all cells selected in >70% of runs), varying proportions of a conservation feature will be protected.

The solution presented below in Figure 3.11 identifies shallow areas on the Cap plateau as well as extending the Flemish Pass/Eastern Canyon closures to the west and the Sackville Spur to the NW and Beothuk Knoll to the north, as the most suitable areas for additional fisheries closure to achieve the 10% target across all conservation features.

Figure 3.32. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 1 (10% target) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

3.5.1.3. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features while minimizing the impact on current fishing activities

The second planning scenario was to determine the minimum area in the Flemish Cap SMA that would be needed for additional fisheries closures to meet a conservation target of 10% for ALL conservation features WHILE minimizing the impact on current fishing activity. Each cell, in addition to the areal cost described in 3.5.1.2 above, was assigned a further cost in the form of a human activity penalty equal to the areal cost weighted by the degree of cumulative impact of fisheries in that cell. If the cell scores a maximum possible human impact index of 1 (where habitats are extremely heavily impacted by fisheries), the cost of the planning unit is doubled, making it much more expensive to include it in the conservation solution. The minimum cost of a planning unit remains the same as in the previous scenario (i.e. the cost is the area of the planning unit) if no fishing impacts are detected. Applying these cell costs not only minimizes impact on fisheries but also incentivises protection of more pristine, unimpacted habitat.

The solution presented below in Figure 3.12 identifies two smaller more discrete shallow areas on the plateau of the Cap as suitable for additional fisheries closure while it removes the area, identified in Figure 3.11, to the south of the Northern Flemish Cap. In terms of planning units selected in 100% of *prioritizr* runs, this scenario represents ~6% increase in

the area required for to meet a 10% conservation target compared to the previous scenario which didn't consider the impact of fisheries.

Figure 3.33. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 2 (10% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

3.5.1.4. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features while minimizing the impact on current fishing activities, taking into account climate change effects and the importance of the SDM at basin scale for conservation.

The third planning scenario determines the minimum area needed to meet a conservation target of 10% for ALL conservation features WHILE minimizing the impact on current fishing activity AND accounting for future climate change effects and considering the importance of the Flemish Cap SMA at the basin scale (Figure 3.34). Each planning unit, in addition to the areal and cumulative impacts costs described in 3.5.1.3 above, was assigned a further ‘climate change’ cost based on the degree of reduction in habitat suitability of a given cell when comparing current and future predicted species/habitat distributions on a scale of 0 (no change) to 1 (future absence). The importance of conservation actions in the Flemish Cap at basin level were also considered by assigning a value on a scale of 0 (no importance) to 1 (high importance) with reference to the basin scale systematic conservation planning solutions produced in D3.4 and Combes et al. (in review). The final cost of a planning unit was discounted up to a maximum of 33%.

Figure 3.34. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 4 (10% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%, climate change penalty of 0-100% and basin scale importance discount of 0-25%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The area needed to reach the conservation target in this scenario increased by 2.6% compared with Scenario 2 (and 8.6% compared with Scenario 1).

Overlaying current fishing activity on the Scenario 4 solution (Figure 3.35) shows that the planning algorithm has done a good job of finding solutions that minimise disruption to fishing. Only the areas selected on the plateau and west of Flemish Pass/Eastern Canyon could result in a requirement for some displacement of fishing effort.

Figure 3.35. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 4 (Figure 3.13) with current fishing activity overlain.

3.5.2. Assess potential future impacts of oil and gas developments at the Flemish Cap

NAFO (2019a) summarized a comprehensive synthesis of trends in offshore petroleum exploration activities in Divs. 3KLMN. According to this synthesis, it is expected (based on current exploration leases and development projections) that offshore oil and gas exploration activities may increase in the NRA until at least 2030. As of 2019, there are four offshore production fields on the Grand Banks, in the Jeanne d’Arc basin area (Div. 3L), and intense exploration activities along the eastern shelf break and Flemish Pass (Divs. 3LM). In 2019-2020, environmental assessments of several Exploration Drilling Projects were completed and these projects can proceed¹².

The total area of Licences¹³ has increased from 2014 to 2019. Figure 3.36 from NAFO (2019a) shows cumulative well counts and Licence areas over time in Divs. 3KLMN. Recent growing in offshore activity is reflected by the steady rise in the number of wells starting in the early 2000s and Licence areas starting in early 2010s.

¹² As an example, in December 2019 was announced that a proposed Flemish Pass Exploration Drilling Project can proceed. This project involves exploration drilling within two offshore Exploration Licences located in the Flemish Pass Basin (see: <https://www.canada.ca/en/impact-assessment-agency/news/2019/12/cnooc-international-flemish-pass-exploration-drilling-project--environmental-assessment-decision.html>).

¹³ Licence types: Exploration, Significant Discovery and Production

Figure 3.36. Trends in offshore oil and gas activities in Divs. 3KLMN. Cumulative number of wells (top panel) and cumulative area of licences (bottom panel). EL (exploration licences), PL (production licences), SDL (significant development licences). Figure from NAFO (2019a), based on C-NLOPB data (www.cnlopb.ca).

Table 4 presents the list of oil and gas projects (different Exploration Drilling Projects and one Development Project) proposed within the NW Atlantic. Figure 3.37 presents the location of the correspondent areas of these proposed projects. The map shows the overlapping of different projects with NAFO fisheries, VME closures and VME polygons in Divs. 3LMN. Despite that the ATLAS exercise on MSP is focused specifically on the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass area, the map suggests that beyond Case Study No11, there are some other areas of interest in the NRA regarding the potential impact of activities other than fishing, particularly human activities linked to hydrocarbon exploration and exploitation (e.g. southern part of Div. 3K, northern slopes of Div. 3N)

Moreover, in February 2020, the Regional Assessment Committee for Exploratory Drilling East of Newfoundland and Labrador of the IAAC¹⁴ reported on Regional Assessment of the effects of existing and anticipated exploratory drilling in the eastern Newfoundland and Labrador offshore. The purpose of the new Regional Assessment is to make it easier for future individual oil and gas exploratory drilling proposals to get their respective

¹⁴ A meeting between the IAAC Regional Assessment Committee and NAFO (WGESA) was held on 26th November 2020, with the aim to present information/input from NAFO on its VMEs (NAFO, 2019a).

environmental approvals for their projects (NAFO, 2019a). The Committee’s Report (Bangay *et al.*, 2020) contains recommendations on requirements for future projects, providing a basis for a new regulatory framework for future offshore oil and gas exploratory activities in the area (<https://iaac-aeic.gc.ca/050/evaluations/exploration?projDocs=80156>).

Table 3.9. List of offshore oil and gas projects proposed within the NW Atlantic. Source: IAAC (April 2020).

Location	Type of project	Status of the Environmental Assessment	Reference in Figure 3.37
Newfoundland Orphan Basin	Exploration Drilling Project	Completed (<i>Decision on Environmental Effects: Feb 2020</i>)	1
Newfoundland Orphan Basin	Exploration Drilling Project	In progress	2
West Flemish Pass	Exploration Drilling Project	In progress	3
Flemish Pass Basin	Exploration Drilling Project	Completed (<i>Decision on Environmental Effects: Apr 2019</i>)	4
Flemish Pass Basin – Bay du Nord	Development Project	In progress	5
Flemish Pass Basin	Exploration Drilling Project	Completed (<i>Decision on Environmental Effects: Dec 2019</i>)	6
Jeanne d’Arc Basin and Flemish Pass Basin	Exploration Drilling Project	Completed (<i>Decision on Environmental Effects: Apr 2019</i>)	7
Flemish Pass – Central Ridge Area	Exploration Drilling Project	In progress	9
Grand Banks	Exploration Drilling Project	Completed (<i>Decision on Environmental Effects: Mar 2020</i>)	10
Jeanne d’Arc Basin – Grand Banks	White Rose Extension Project	Completed (<i>Decision on Environmental Effects: Sep 2013</i>)	11
Jeanne d’Arc Basin – Grand Banks (Tilt Cove)	Exploration Drilling Project	In progress	12
Southeastern Newfoundland (Carson Basin)	Exploration Drilling Project	In progress	13

Cordes *et al.* (2016) summarized the different steps involving deep-water exploration. According to these authors, exploration activities start with (i) *seismic surveys* to understand the subsurface geology and potential hydrocarbon reservoirs. If suitable targets are detected, (ii) *exploration wells* are drilled to ground-truth the interpretation of the acoustic data. If economically recoverable hydrocarbon reserves are located, the site may advance to production. Development of the production, typically involves the drilling of (iii) *appraisal wells* followed by (iv) *production wells* and the (v) *installation of various infrastructure*, in the surface (e.g. drill ships as FPSO vessels) and subsea (e.g., manifolds, control cables, and export lines). In a deep-sea production field, the various wells are connected together with a series of pipes and control cables (Hyne, 2001).

The expected increased demand for oil and gas discovered in the NRA (Figure 3.36 and Figure 3.37; Table 3.9) suggests that potential high seas and transboundary conflicts – related to the process described above – could arise in the future. Moreover, as was noted by Cordes *et al.* (2016), oil and gas activities can have detrimental environmental effects during each of the main phases of exploration, production, and decommissioning.

Figure 3.37. Map of the NAFO Regulatory Area (Divs. 3KLN), showing the location of the proposed Oil and Gas Project Areas listed in Table 4, and the overlapping with NAFO fisheries, VME closures and VME polygons in Divs. 3LNM. The red polygon in Divs. 3LM, indicates the location of the Flemish Pass Basin – Bay du Nord Development Project. EDP (Exploration Drilling Project Area), DP (Development Project Area). Sources (2019): NAFO and C- NLOPB website.

3.6. Evaluation of management effectiveness and recommend adaptations to current management in the light of climate change (MESMA Steps 6 and 7).

3.6.1. Expanded MPA network and climate change

3.6.1.1. Expanded MPA network to meet 30% area target and climate change

The UN Convention of Biological Diversity (CDB) Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework sets out an ambitious plan to implement broad-based action to bring about a transformation in society’s relationship with biodiversity and to ensure that, by 2050, the shared vision of living in harmony with nature is fulfilled. The framework is intended to contribute to the implementation of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

While the UN Sustainable Development Goal 14, Aichi Target 1, calls for 10% Marine Protected Area coverage globally by 2020, negotiations are underway to set new targets for

adoption in the Post-2020 Global Biodiversity Framework¹⁵. The International Union for Conservation Network (IUCN) membership have approved a new global target for MPAs of setting aside “30% of each marine habitat” in “highly protected MPAs and other effective area-based conservation measures” by 2030. Although the 30%-by-2030 target is not binding on nations, the European Union has already embraced it as a goal in its recently published EU Biodiversity Strategy for 2030 Report¹⁶.

To test what a 30% by 2030 conservation target might look like in the Flemish Cap SMA we ran a systematic conservation planning exercise for a CBD 2030 scenario which used the same costs (area, cumulative impacts and climate change effects) and basin scale importance discounts as applied in Scenario 4 in 3.5.1.4 above, but with a 30% rather than a 10% conservation target, and “locking in” the previous 10% solution as a starting point, rather than just using the existing fisheries closures network. The resulting conservation solution is presented in **Error! Reference source not found.** The 30% solution with the configuration of costs and penalties used here, connects a number of the existing fisheries closures: 1) Northern Flemish Cap (shallower part), Northeast Flemish cap, Eastern Flemish Cap and Beathuk Knoll and extends the area proposed under the 10% solution on the plateau; 2) Sackville Spur and Northern Flemish Cap (deeper parts); 3) Flemish Pass/Eastern Canyon to include Northwest Flemish Cap as well as extending northwards out along the slope.

Figure 3.38. The degree of protection offered under SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (30% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%, climate change penalty of 0-100% and basin scale importance discount of 0-25%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

¹⁵ www.cbd.int/article/zero-draft-update-august-2020

¹⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/environment/nature/biodiversity/strategy/index_en.htm

Figure 3.39. The SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (Figure 3.17) overlain with current fishing activity.

3.6.2. Oil and gas exploration and climate change

Overlaying current oil and gas concessions on the CBD 2030 conservation solution (Figure 3.40. SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (Figure 3.17) with an overlay of current oil and gas exploration, significant discovery and production licence blocks.) shows that exploration activities in areas that have been identified as priority areas for future expansion of conservation efforts may require more stringent environmental impact assessments prior to commencing new operations. Because the current conservation efforts are sectoral, i.e. management of fisheries under the NAFO Regulatory Framework, it would suggest that a more holistic management framework is required either through bi-lateral arrangements or perhaps through the establishment of an overarching management framework as part of the proposed UN BBNJ regulation and overseen by the Conference of the Parties (COP).

Figure 3.40. SCP CBD 2030 Scenario (Figure 3.17) with an overlay of current oil and gas exploration, significant discovery and production licence blocks.

Ultimately, there is a clear imperative to wind-down the search for new hydrocarbon reserves if we are to meet IPCC global CO₂ mitigation targets.

3.7. Governance (MESMA Step 8)

3.7.1. Utility of MSP in the NAFO Regulatory Area

ATLAS work developed in Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass addresses, for the first time in the NAFO context, the current challenges facing MSP in the NRA, including the issue of the seabed litter (NAFO, 2018; 2019a; 2019b). Moreover, following the recommendations from NAFO Commission (NAFO, 2019c), ATLAS research on the impact of human activities other than fishing has been incorporated into Ecosystem Summary Sheets (ESSs) (NAFO, 2019a). ESSs are part of NAFO Roadmap for an Ecosystem Approach to Fisheries, and will be used to inform decision making, by both managers and industry, as well as help identify objective hazards in the NRA (e.g. oil and gas exploration and exploitation). The ESSs will be presented to the Commission in September 2020 and are intended to provide a synoptic perspective on the state of NAFO ecosystems and their management regime. They constitute a tool for strategic assessment, advice, and planning for the Northwest Atlantic Ocean in ABNJ. ATLAS results (i.e. maps) show the potential spatial conflicts from different human activities. These results have contributed to several sections of the ESS including (i) VME status, (ii) oil and gas activities and (iii) pollution, specifically marine litter. Additionally, seabed litter pilot study in Flemish Pass (García-Alegre *et al.*, 2020) could be a start point to

marine litter monitoring in the NRA (NAFO, 2019a), contributing to the knowledge on GES. All this work contributes to explore the feasibility of MSP in the NRA.

As Wright *et al.* (2019) suggested the emergence of MSP as a key tool for ecosystem-based management of marine spaces provide a clear impetus for developing MSP in ABNJ. In the case of the NRA, besides the ATLAS efforts to address the challenges of integrated spatial management, interest in MSP seems to be growing. In this regard, a Webinar ATLAS-DFO on MSP was held on 5th March 2020. During the meeting, ATLAS scientists presented (i) ATLAS regional MSP studies, (ii) MSP decision support tools and workflow developed by the project, and (iii) an overview of the MSP exercise conducted for the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass.

3.7.2. MSP as a potential tool to help resolve conflicts: connection with Blue Economy - Blue Growth

As pointed out by Arbo and Thuy (2016), environmental and resource use conflicts are frequently about the access to and use of natural resources and marine space and the distribution of the associated benefits and costs. They can also be about the harm that different co-located activities inflict upon each other through operational or ecosystem impact. Moreover, the conflicts can involve both actual and potential users. The authors conclude that resolving use conflicts is a central issue in the context of ecosystem-based management. For the industries involved, this is important for avoiding intractable conflicts, but it is also important for the health of the ecosystems.

Preliminary mapping of human activities and natural components in the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass area shows that some of the potential use conflicts mentioned by Arbo and Thuy (2016) could arise in the future in this area (Figure 3.36). Moreover, information on a recent transboundary oil spill (Table 3.9) suggests that actual conflicts already occurred.

In an expected scenario of increasing oil and gas exploration activities in the NRA (NAFO, 2019a), a comprehensive spatial management plan could help to maximize compatibility between traditional and emerging activities, reducing conflicts between users and between users and the marine environment.

MSP could be used as a framework to achieve better management and spatial use of marine environment in ABNJ and several options could be adopted to properly implement MSP in ABNJ, as Altvater *et al.* (2019) suggested. MSP could help to resolve specific conflicts, contributing to the objective of ensuring that ecosystems continue to perform their functions (Thurber *et al.*, 2014), providing, in addition to oil and gas, goods and services as important as fish, habitats and VMEs (Armstrong *et al.*, 2010). This highlights the benefits of spatial management, making explicit the connection between MSP and *Blue Economy - Blue Growth*.

3.7.3. Reflections on ocean governance: VMEs are closed to fishing but open to oil and gas

Mapping exercise from ATLAS project in the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass Case Study (Figure 3.29, Figure 3.37), revealed the overlap (and potential conflicts) between different management frameworks. Areas closed to bottom fishing by NAFO to conserve VMEs, are currently open to offshore oil and gas exploration and exploitation. It is worth to note that the VME concept arose in the context of the management of deep-sea bottom fisheries in the high seas (FAO, 2009) and it does not apply to other human activities. VMEs within NAFO

VME closures are currently protected against significant adverse impacts from bottom fishing, but they are unprotected regarding potential threats from human activities other than fishing, including the potential impacts from offshore oil and gas (Cordes *et al.*, 2016; Girard and Fisher, 2018; Vad *et al.*, 2016). This seems an inconsistency in terms of VME conservation and ocean governance. The conflicts mentioned above, are related to the institutional landscape (cf. 3.1.1.2). High seas fisheries occur in the international water column and they are managed by NAFO, in a collaborative multilateral framework, according to the International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Fisheries in the High Seas (FAO, 2009), while offshore oil and gas activities on the extended continental shelf are managed by the coastal state. Each sector has its own independent management process and the coordination between management authorities is often limited. In this case, MSP as a participatory process involving stakeholders, could help to resolve conflicts and inconsistencies.

3.7.4. Lack of an appropriate authority needed to undertake MSP in ABJN

Besides governance issues (see Durán Muñoz *et al.*, 2020b: section 8.3) and technical difficulties (see Durán Muñoz *et al.*, 2020b: section 8.5), the lack of an appropriate authority needed to undertake MSP in ABJN (cf. 3.1.1.2) was identified as the principal practical problem in the NRA. According to the UNESCO, one of the first tasks of MSP is the identification and establishment of the appropriate kind of authority needed to undertake MSP. Ehler *et al.* (2009) suggest that while planning without implementation is sterile, implementation without planning is a recipe for failure. Therefore MSP requires two types of authority: (i) authority to plan for MSP; and (ii) authority to implement MSP. Both types are equally important. They could be combined in one organization, but in most MSP initiatives around the world, new authority is often established for MSP, while implementation is carried out through existing authorities and institutions. One suggested way to establish authority for MSP planning is through the creation of new legislation. Therefore, in order to develop and implement a spatial management plan integrating fishing and hydrocarbon activities in the NRA, as it is located in ABNJ, an international agreement on what type of authority is most appropriate, should be necessary. This is the case of all MSP initiatives in ABJN.

3.8. Conclusions

- ATLAS is developing a theoretical exercise of MSP in the Flemish Cap – Flemish Pass area, Divs. 3LM (NRA – ABJN), using MESMA framework: the first time that MSP issue is discussed in NAFO.
- Natural components of the ecosystem and human activities have been preliminarily mapped in a GIS.
- Potential and real conflicts between different users of the marine space (traditional *versus* emergent) and between users and ecosystems have been identified in the NRA.
- MSP is a potential tool to help resolve conflicts. Moreover, the present exercise is useful to the advice on the impact of human activities other than fishing in the NRA (e.g. Ecosystem Summary Sheets).
- Reflections and practical problems: VME are closed to bottom fishing, but open to other human activities; According to the UNESCO an appropriate authority is needed for developing and implement MSP in ABJN (water column *vs* extended continental shelf).

3.9. Acknowledgements

The EU NAFO groundfish surveys has been co-funded by the European Union through the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund within the National Program of collection, management and use of data in the fisheries sector and support for scientific advice regarding the Common Fisheries Policy. The authors in addition to ATLAS (PDM, MS & AGA) were supported by NEREIDA grant agreement SI2.770786 (PDM & MS) and IEO-BIOPESE-4 (ER). We are especially grateful to all people (from IEO and foreign institutions) that helped us to compile information on ecosystem components.

3.10. Bibliography

- Altvater S., Fletcher R., Passarello C. (2019) The Need for Marine Spatial Planning in Areas Beyond National Jurisdiction. *In: Zaucha J., Gee K. (eds) Maritime Spatial Planning*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Arbo, P. and Thuy P.T.T. (2016). Use conflicts in marine ecosystem-based management — The case of oil versus fisheries. *Ocean & Coastal Management*. 122. 77-86. 10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2016.01.008.
- Ardron, J., Gjerde, K., Pullen, S. and Tilot, V. (2008). Marine Spatial Planning in the High Seas. *Marine Policy* 32: 832-839. doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2008.03.018.
- Armstrong, C. W., Foley, N., Tinch, R., and v.d. Hove, S. (2010) Ecosystem Goods and Services of the Deep Sea, HERMIONE (Hotspot Ecosystem Research and Man's impact on European Seas), Deliverable D6.2: Ecosystem Goods and Services of the Deep Sea, WP6: Socioeconomics, Ocean Governance and Science-Policy Interfaces, 2010.
- Bangay G., Foote, W., Anderson G., Murphy Rustad M., and Storey K. (2020) Committee's Report on the Regional Assessment of Offshore Oil and Gas Exploratory Drilling East of Newfoundland and Labrador. 196 pp. Accessed on 13 May 2020 from <https://iaac-aeic.gc.ca/050/documents/p80156/134068E.pdf>
- Buhl-Mortensen, L., Galparsoro, I., Vega Fernandez, T., Johnson, K., D'Anna, G., & Badalamenti, F., Garofalo, G., Carlström, J., Piwowarczyk, J., Rabaut, M., Vanaverbeke, J., Schipper, C., van Dalssen, J., Vassilopoulou, V., Issaris, Y., Van Hoof, L., Pecceu, E., Hostens, K., Zammit Pace, M. L., and Doncheva, V. (2016) Maritime ecosystem-based management in practice: Lessons learned from the application of a generic spatial planning framework in Europe. *Marine Policy*. 10.1016/j.marpol.2016.01.024.
- Callery, O., Grehan, A. Stirling, D. (2020). Cumulative environmental impact analysis in 12 ATLAS case studies. Atlas Milestone 30 Report.
- Cordes, E.E., Jones, D.O.B., Schlacher, T.A., Amon, D.J., Bernardino, A.F., Brooke, S., Carney, R., DeLeo, D.M., Dunlop, K.M., Escobar-Briones, E.G., Gates, A.R., Génio, L., Gobin, J., Henry, L.-A., Herrera, S., Hoyt, S., Joye, M., Kark, S., Mestre, N.C., Metaxas, A., Pfeifer, S., Sink, K., Sweetman, A.K., Witte, U. (2016). Environmental impacts of the deep-water oil and gas industry: a review to guide management strategies. *Frontiers in Environmental Science* 4. 10.3389/fenvs.2016.00058.
- Durán Muñoz, P., Sacau, M., García-Alegre, A. and Román, E. (2020a) Cold-water corals and deep-sea sponges by-catch mitigation: Dealing with groundfish survey data in the management of the northwest Atlantic Ocean high seas fisheries, *Marine Policy* 116, 103712. 10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103712.
- Durán Muñoz, P., Sacau, M., Román-Marcote, E. and García-Alegre, A. (2020). A theoretical exercise of Marine Spatial Planning in the Flemish Cap and Flemish Pass (NAFO Divs. 3LM): implications for fisheries management in the high seas. NAFO SCR Doc. 20/022. pp 25.
- Ehler, C. y Douvère, F. (2009). Planificación espacial marina: una guía paso a paso hacia la Gestión Ecosistémica. Comisión Oceanográfica Intergubernamental y el Programa del Hombre y la Biosfera. COI manuales y guías no 53. París, UNESCO. 2009 (inglés). 2013 (español).
- FAO (2009) International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-Sea Fisheries in the High Seas, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, 2009.
- García-Alegre A., Román-Marcote E., Gago J., González-Nuevo G., Sacau M., Durán Muñoz P. (2020). Seabed litter distribution in the high-seas of the Flemish Pass area (NW Atlantic). *Sci. Mar.* 84(1): 93-101. <https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.04945.27A>.
- Girard, F. and Fisher, C. (2018) Long-term impact of the Deepwater Horizon oil spill on deep-sea corals detected after seven years of monitoring. *Biological Conservation* 225, 117-127. 10.1016/j.biocon.2018.06.028.
- Halpern, B.S., Walbridge, S., Selkoe, K.A., Kappel, C.V., Micheli, F., D'Agrosa, C., Bruno, J.F., Casey, K.S., Ebert, C., Fox, H.E., Fujita R., Heinemann, D., Lenihan, H.S., Madin, E.M.P., Perry, M.T., Selig, E.R., Spalding, M., Steneck, R., and Watson, R. (2008). A Global Map of Human Impact on Marine Ecosystems. *Science* 319 (5865): 948– 952, doi.org/10.1126/science.1149345.

- Hyne, N.J. (2001) Non-technical Guide to Petroleum Geology, Exploration, Drilling and Production. PennWell Corporation, Tulsa: OK.
- Kenchington, E., Murillo, F.J., Lirette, C., Sacau, M., Koen-Alonso, M., Kenny, A., Ollerhead, N., Wareham, V., Beazley, L. (2014) Kernel density surface modelling as a means to identify significant concentrations of vulnerable marine ecosystem indicators, *PLoS One* 9 (10) (2014), e109365, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0109365>.
- Kellner, JB, Tetreault, I., Gaines, SD, Nisbet, RM (2007). Fishing the line near marine reserves in single and multi-species fisheries. *Ecological Applications* 17:1039–1054.
- Kroodsma, D.A., Mayorga, J., Hochberg, T., Miller, N.A., Boerder, K., Ferretti, F., Wilson, A., Bergman, B., White, T.D., Block, B.A., Woods, P., Sullivan, B., Costello, C., Worm, B., 2018. Tracking the global footprint of fisheries. *Science* 359, 904–908. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aao5646>
- Long, R. and Rodriguez Chaves, M. (2015) Anatomy of a new international instrument for conservation and biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction. *Environmental Liability — Law, Policy and Practice* 23: 213–229.
- Maes, F. (2008) The international framework for marine spatial planning. *Marine Policy* 32: 797-810.
- NAFO (2018) Report of the 11th Meeting of the NAFO Scientific Council Working Group on Ecosystem Science and Assessment (WG-ESA). Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization. 13-22 November 2018, Dartmouth, Canada. Serial No N6900 NAFO SCS Document 18/23.
- NAFO (2019a) Report of the 12th Meeting of the NAFO Scientific Council Working Group on Ecosystem Science and Assessment (WG-ESA). Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization. 19-28 November 2019, Dartmouth, Canada. Serial No. N7027 NAFO SCS Document 19/25.
- NAFO (2019b) Report of the NAFO Joint Commission-Scientific Council Working Group on the Ecosystem Approach Framework to Fisheries Management (WG-EAFFM). Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization. 16-18 July 2019, Dartmouth, Canada. Serial No. N6971 NAFO COM-SC Document 19-03.
- NAFO (2019c) Report of the NAFO Commission and its Subsidiary Bodies (STACTIC and STACFAD). Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization. 41st Annual Meeting of NAFO. 23-27 September 2019 Bordeaux, France. Serial No. N7021 NAFO/COM Doc. 19-34.
- NAFO (2020) Conservation and Enforcement Measures, Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization, 2020. Serial No. N7028. NAFO/Com Document 20-01.
- QGIS Development Team (2019). QGIS Geographic Information System. Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project. <http://qgis.osgeo.org>.
- Stelzenmüller *et al.* (2013). Monitoring and evaluation of spatially managed areas: A generic framework for implementation of ecosystem based marine management and its application. *Marine Policy* 37: 149–164. doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2012.04.012.
- Stock, A., 2016. Open Source Software for Mapping Human Impacts on Marine Ecosystems with an Additive Model. *Journal of Open Research Software*, 4(1), p.e21. doi.org/10.5334/jors.88.
- Thurber, A. R., Sweetman, A.K., Narayanaswamy, B. E., Jones, D. O. B., Ingels, J., and, Hansman R. L. (2014) Ecosystem function and services provided by the deep sea. *Biogeosciences*, 11, 3941–3963, doi.org/10.5194/bg-11-3941-2014
- Vad, J., Kazanidis, G., Henry, L.A., Jones, D.O.B., Tendal, O.S., Christiansen, S., Henry, T.B. and Roberts, JM (2016) Potential Impacts of Offshore Oil and Gas Activities on Deep-Sea Sponges and the Habitats They Form. *in Advances in Marine Biology* 79, Elsevier, pp. 33-60. [10.1016/bs.amb.2018.01.001](https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.amb.2018.01.001)
- Wright, G., Gjerde, K., Johnson, D., Finkelstein, A., Ferreira, M.A., Dunn, D., Chaves, M. And Grehan, A. (2019). Marine spatial planning in areas beyond national jurisdiction. *Marine Policy*. [10.1016/j.marpol.2018.12.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2018.12.003).

4. Rockall Bank Case Study

4.1. Context Setting

4.1.1. Set boundaries for Spatial Managed Area (SMA) Assessment (MESMA 1a)

4.1.1.1. *Description of the Case Study Area*

Rockall Bank lies approximately 400 km to the west of Scotland and is the largest, shallowest and best studied of several banks that form the Faroese-Rockall Plateau. It rises from Rockall Trough (> 2000 m) in the east and north and breaks the surface towards the northern end of the bank in the form of a small islet known as Rockall. To the west it rises from a shallower basin and depths of around 1 km and to the south from the abyssal Atlantic. Rockall Bank is located at the boundary between two counter rotating gyres; the subtropical and subpolar gyres of the North Atlantic (McGrath et al. 2012). As a result, the oceanography of Rockall Bank is dominated by the dynamics of the subpolar gyre (SPG), where changes in the strength and extent of the SPG dictate the marine climate (Hátún et al. 2009, Berx & Payne 2017).

Rockall Bank has a long history of fisheries exploitation as well as being the subject of hydrographic, oceanographic and fisheries surveys for many years (Johnson et al., 2019). Although there are no oil and gas developments on Rockall Bank, the granting of frontier exploration licenses in the recent licensing rounds, and a reanalysis of old well data in the light of new information, has spurred renewed interest in the region (Broadley et al. 2020).

Diverse offshore habitats found on and around Rockall Bank support rich aggregations of benthic invertebrates, such as long-lived and fragile cold-water coral reef ecosystems and sponge aggregations, as well as a diverse fish assemblage (Roberts et al. 2008, Neat & Campbell 2011). Areas that constitute vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs) (FAO, 2009) are found on Rockall Bank and the recognition and protection of these has contributed to a complex arrangement of management areas in the region (reviewed by Johnson et al., 2019).

4.1.1.2. *Institutional Landscape*

This area lies partially within the EEZ of the EU and partially within the ABNJ. That part within the EU's EEZ is managed under the EU's Common Fisheries Policy. That part in the ABNJ is managed by the competent regional fisheries management organisation, the North East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC). The seabed lies within the extended continental shelf claim of the United Kingdom and the Republic of Ireland. There are spatial management plans for the conservation of VMEs in the area that include areas closed by NEAFC to protect Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems (UN Resolutions 61/105 and 64/72), Special Areas of Conservation (under the EU Habitats Directive and Natura 2000) and marine protected areas (UK/EU/OSPAR).

4.1.1.3. *Rockall Bank Spatial Managed Area*

At present there is no single integrated management plan for the Rockall area. There is clear political demarcation of boundaries between the ABNJ and that within the EEZ of the EU.

The boundary of the SMA is focussed on the Rockall plateau where there is good data and the main fisheries and closed areas (Figure 4. 1).

Figure 4. 1. Detail of the Rockall Bank Spatially Managed Area (delimited in red).

4.1.2. Define goals and operational objectives for the SMA (MESMA 1b)

4.1.2.1. Blue Growth Goals

The main blue economy sector for the Rockall area is fisheries. However, fisheries currently operate in relation to environmental objectives for the protection of vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs) and the potential goods and services they provide. Oil and Gas, is considered as a possible future sector in a hypothetical scenario. The area is too far offshore to provide economically viable renewable energy and there are no major transatlantic cables within the case study area, although they pass through the wider area. Fisheries have the potential to grow in this area provided they can demonstrate they have no adverse impacts on VMEs in the area and are done in such a way as to ensure long term sustainable harvesting.

4.1.2.2. Operational Objectives

- Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of a network of marine protected areas
- Maintain current fisheries at or close to MSY taking into account wider ecosystem impacts.
- Assess potential impacts of oil and gas developments

4.2. Collate and map existing information

4.2.1. Identify ecosystem components (MESMA 2a)

4.2.1.1. Habitats

The realisation of sustainable Blue Growth and efforts to conserve the marine environment require information on the distribution of marine habitats. The EUSeaMap is a broad-scale predictive mapping initiative that harmonises mapping procedures, based on the EUNIS classification, and provides a comprehensive map of marine habitats for all European basins from the Barents Sea to Macaronesia and to the Black Sea (Populus et al. 2017). The EUSeaMap was used to define the broad-scale habitat types occurring within the Rockall Bank case study with 17 different habitats being present (Figure 4.2). These were included as ecosystem components in the analyses presented here (Table 4. 1).

Table 4. 1. EUSeaMap habitat classification descriptions and the associated EUNIS habitat code for marine habitats within the Rockall Bank case study.

<u>EUSeaMap Name</u>	<u>EUNIS Code and Name</u>	<u>EU SeaMap Description (Biozone and substrate)</u>	<u>EUNIS description</u>
Atlantic mid bathyal rock or other hard substrata	A6.11	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on rock or other hard substrata, biogenic reef also present	Deep sea bedrock
Atlantic mid bathyal mixed substrata	A6.2	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on mixed sediment	Deep sea mixed substrate
Atlantic upper bathyal rock or other hard substrata	A6.11	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on rock or other hard substrata, biogenic reef also present	Deep sea bedrock
Atlantic upper bathyal mixed substrata	A6.2	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on mixed sediment	Deep sea mixed substrate
Atlantic mid bathyal sand	A6.3	Atlantic mid or upper bathyal, low energy, on sand	Deep sea sand
Atlantic mid bathyal mud or sandy mud to muddy sand	A6.4	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on sandy mud to muddy sand	Deep sea muddy sand
Atlantic upper bathyal mud or sandy mud to muddy sand	A6.4 or A6.5	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low to moderate energy, Mud to muddy sand	Deep sea muddy sand/sand
Atlantic lower bathyal mud or sandy mud to muddy sand	A6.4 or A6.5	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low to moderate energy, Mud to muddy sand	Deep sea muddy sand/sand
Atlantic lower bathyal mixed substrata	A6.2	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on mixed sediment	Deep sea mixed substrate
A5.37 (Offshore circalittoral mud)	A5.37	Deep circalittoral, low, medium or high energy (mostly Mud to sandy mud or sandy mud to muddy sand)	Deep sea circalittoral mud
A5.15 (offshore circalittoral coarse sediment)	A5.15	offshore circalittoral coarse sediment produced at mostly moderate energy, deep circalittoral, coarse sediment	Deep sea circalittoral coarse sediment
A4.33 (offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef produced at low energy)	A4.33	offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef produced at low energy, on rock or other hard substrata	Faunal communities on deep low energy circalittoral rock

<u>EUSeaMap Name</u>	<u>EUNIS Code and Name</u>	<u>EU SeaMap Description (Biozone and substrate)</u>	<u>EUNIS description</u>
A4.27 (offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef produced at moderate energy)	A4.27	offshore circalittoral rock and biogenic reef produced at moderate energy, on rock or other hard substrata	Faunal communities on deep moderate energy circalittoral rock
Atlantic lower bathyal rock or other hard substrata	A6.11	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on rock or other hard substrata, biogenic reef also present	Deep sea bedrock
Atlantic upper bathyal sand	A6.3	Atlantic mid or upper bathyal, low energy, on sand,	Deep sea sand
A5.27	A5.27	Offshore circalittoral sand, low energy, deep circalittoral, sand substrate	Deep circalittoral sand
Atlantic upper bathyal sandy mud to muddy sand	A6.4	Atlantic bathyal (low, mid or upper), low energy, on sandy mud to muddy sand	Deep sea muddy sand

Figure 4. 2. Example of an EUSeaMap habitat included that has been included as an ecosystem component in the analyses presented here (EUNIS code and description: A5.37, Deep sea circalittoral mud; EUSeaMap description: Deep circalittoral, low, medium or high energy (mostly Mud to sandy mud or sandy mud to muddy sand).

4.2.1.2. Vulnerable Marine Ecosystem indicator species and habitats

In 2006, the United Nations General Assembly (UNGA) called upon States and Regional Fisheries Management Organisations (RFMOs) to identify areas where vulnerable marine

ecosystems (VMEs) occur, or are likely to occur, and to make efforts to prevent significant adverse impacts to them (UNGA 2006). Subsequently, the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) issued guidance for the management of deep-sea fisheries in the high seas, including defining criteria as to what represents a VME (Morato et al. 2018). These criteria are: 1. uniqueness or rarity; 2. functional significance of the habitat; 3. fragility; 4. life history traits of component species that make recovery difficult; and 6. structural complexity (FAO 2009). The Joint ICES/NAFO Working Group on Deep-water Ecology (WGDEC) maintains a central database on the distribution and abundance of habitats and species considered to be indicators of vulnerable marine ecosystems (VMEs) across the North Atlantic. This ICES VME database aims to store and make available all known VME indicator records in the North Atlantic (for deep water areas inside and outside national jurisdiction) (e.g. ICES 2020). Here we utilise this database to map the occurrence of VME indicators and habitats within the Rockall Bank case study, including: gorgonians, black coral, stony coral, deep-sea sponge aggregations, cup coral, Stylasterids, stony coral and sea-pens. An example is provided in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3. Gorgonian records from the ICES VME database within the Rockall Bank case study.

4.2.1.3. Predictive models

A further set of ecosystem components, based on predictive distribution models, were also included for the case study. Full details of this work are given in ATLAS Deliverable 3.3: *Biodiversity, biogeography and GOODS classification system under current climate conditions and future IPCC scenarios*, but a brief summary is provided here. Species distribution models were constructed for three benthic invertebrate species on Rockall bank; *Lophelia pertusa* and two sea pen species (*Funiculina quadrangularis* and *Ptilella greyi*). Records of occurrence for the three species of interest were taken from the ICES VME database to which MSS reports all encounters of VME indicator species made on the various

cruises undertaken within the Rockall area. A suite of environmental layers were derived for the area including information on the physical and chemical composition of the water surrounding Rockall Bank, information on the composition of the sediments across Rockall Bank as well as an analysis of the terrain derived from bathymetric information. Given that all areas of Rockall Bank have not been sampled equally, a further layer (derived from information on the spatial distribution of fishing activity across the bank) was used to condition the models in an attempt to account for any ‘sampling’ bias. A point process modelling (PPM) framework was used to jointly model both the location and number of presence points as a function of the environmental variables for each of the three species of interest, with the response being the intensity of points per unit area. The model domain for each of the species was derived from the extent of the presence records. Predictions were made across Rockall bank along with 95% confidence intervals. A binary surface was derived from the model predictions at the threshold where sensitivity and specificity were maximised and these binary surfaces were included here as ecosystem components (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.4. Example of a predictive model binary surface (for *Lophelia pertusa*) used as an ecosystem component in the analyses presented here.

4.2.1.4. Fish distribution

The evolution of the fishery at Rockall Bank is described by Newton *et al.* (2008). The earliest records of fishing at Rockall are of Shetland fishermen fishing for cod (*Gadus morhua*) using handlines in 1805. The main target species switched from cod to haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) at the beginning of the 20th century with the advent of steam powered trawlers. Interest in the fishing grounds at Rockall was sporadic until the later part of the 20th century when pressure on existing stocks within EU territorial limits, and the

extension of exclusive economic zones to 200 miles, meant commercial interest in in fishing at Rockall increased. Marine Scotland Science, a division within the Scottish Government (formally a governmental agency: Fisheries Research Services), has maintained an independent fisheries survey – the Rockall haddock survey – on a near yearly basis since 1985 on Rockall Bank. During the survey, 30-minute bottom trawls are conducted and the entire catch is processed by identifying to species, counting and recording the length frequencies of each species present and also the combined weight for each species. While the main purpose of the survey is to monitor commercial fish stocks on Rockall Bank, the data arising from it represents a valuable biodiversity resource for the fish assemblage associated with the bank.

It is often useful to spatially aggregate point data, such as those arising from the mid-point of the trawls undertaken during the Rockall haddock survey, into discrete areal units. Data from the Rockall haddock survey were used to map the distribution of fish species across the Rockall Bank case study by spatially aggregating the mid-point of the trawls over a hexagonal grid. The spatial resolution for the grid was chosen by examining the effect changing the grid cell size had on the correlations between fish and VME diversity indices (derived using the ICES VME database). A resolution of 14.25 km² gave an optimal trade-off between correlations while still preserving a fine enough spatial scale to be informative (Figure 4.5A). This resulted in binary distribution maps for 92 species of fish across Rockall Bank that have been included here as ecosystem components (e.g. Figure 4.5B).

Figure 4.5. A. Total numbers of monkfish (*Lophius piscatorius*) and B. binary map included in the analyses as an ecosystem component.

4.2.2. Identify human activities, pressures and impacts (MESMA 2b)

4.2.2.1. Fisheries

Fishing is, and always has been, one of the main activities that humans use to benefit from the planet's primary productivity (Swartz et al. 2010). In the modern world, seafood is a globally traded commodity that is vital for world food security and its importance is only expected to increase in the face of increases in global population and the challenges associated with a changing climate (Watson & Tidd 2018). Already, however, the impacts associated with fishing, particularly from mobile bottom-contacting gears, are thought to make it the most pervasive anthropogenic pressure impacting benthic environments (Halpern et al. 2008, Kroodsmas et al. 2018). Interactions between mobile bottom-contacting fishing

gear and the seabed results in the removal of or damage to fragile benthic epifauna, which can precipitate changes to the structure and function of the benthic community (Kaiser et al. 2006, Kenchington et al. 2007, Hiddink et al. 2017). The effects of fishing on deep-sea benthic environments are thought to be even more severe due to the tendency for deep-sea invertebrates to be exceptionally long-lived with extremely slow growth rates, resulting in a highly limited and prolonged recovery capacity (Clark et al. 2016).

Rockall Bank is highly productive due to the upwelling of nutrients from the deeper surrounding areas, which support large fish stocks that have a long history of exploitation (Newton et al. 2008, Neat & Campbell 2011). Fishing is the main anthropogenic activity taking place at Rockall, with the main fishery being for haddock. This is almost totally a trawl fishery and is prosecuted by vessels from the EU and Russian Federation, with the UK (Scotland) accounting for over 80% of the total landings in 2015 (Jones et al. 2018). While the stock dynamics of haddock at Rockall have been volatile, it is a profitable fishery and was certified as meeting the standards of sustainability by the Marine Stewardship Council in 2018 (Jones et al. 2018, Johnson et al. 2019) (Figure 4.6). Other important non-target species of economic importance in this mixed demersal fishery include; whiting, monkfish and ling. The Rockall haddock fishery is limited to ICES division 6b and the EU agrees a Total Allowable Catch limit for its vessels based on ICES advice which is conditioned on the Maximum Sustainable Yield approach (e.g. ICES 2019).

Figure 4.6. The value of the fishery with the Rockall Bank case study for the years 2009 - 2016, based on ICES VMS and log book data.

4.2.2.2. Oil and Gas

While there is currently no active oil and gas sector activity at Rockall, exploratory drilling in the surrounding areas occurred during a 25-year period between 1980 – 2006, with one sub-commercial gas accumulation discovered from the 12 wells drilled (Schofield et al. 2018). Failure to discover key strata of Jurassic age in any of the exploratory drilling has led to a widely held and negative commercial view of the region holding viable hydrocarbon reserves. However, the UK Oil and Gas Authority released new 2D seismic data for the region in 2016 this, along with a reanalysis of the past exploratory well data, has led to a

resurgence in calls for exploration in the area by the UK's oil and gas sector (Broadley et al. 2020).

4.2.3. Identify existing management measures (MESMA 2c)

Rockall Bank has a complicated management history, with marine governance of the area recently being described as a *super wicked* problem (Johnson et al. 2019). This is because it straddles national and international waters, which brings a suite of competing and confounding regulations and makes the development of holistic sustainable management plan for the area fraught with difficulty (Johnson et al. 2019). In 1977, UK fishing limits were extended from 12 to 200 nautical miles as the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP) of the EC was transposed in UK law and Rockall was used as the western most base point, greatly expanding the EU EEZ into the North East Atlantic. This effectively excluded all non-EU nations from fishing at Rockall Bank, which was managed exclusively under the CFP. However, in 1998 the use of Rockall as a base point was deemed in contravention of UNCLOS as it is an uninhabitable islet (Newton et al. 2008). The result of this was a redrawing of the UK/EU EEZ, using St. Kilda as the most westerly base point, and a resulting change to the fisheries limits and management regimes across Rockall Bank. Currently, the eastern portion of the Bank remains within the EU EEZ (UK and Irish) and is managed under the CFP (at the time of writing it remains unclear how the UK exiting the EU will affect this management going forward). The western periphery of the Bank falls within the area of the competent RFMO; the North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission (NEAFC). Rockall Bank remains politically divisive, with interested parties (UK, Ireland, Faroe Islands / Denmark and Iceland) engaged in a protracted boundary dispute relating to the respective claims to continental shelf rights in the region (Yiallourides 2018). The arrangement of the spatially managed areas on Rockall Bank are shown in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7. Arrangement of the spatially managed areas on Rockall Bank.

4.2.3.1. Rockall Haddock Box

The first spatially managed area on Rockall Bank was put in place jointly by NEAFC (in 2001) and the EU (in 2002), to protect the juvenile component of the haddock stock in response to concerns over the declining stock and the increased access to the area following the change of fisheries limits in the region – the Rockall Haddock Box (RHB) (Newton et al. 2008, Johnson et al. 2019) (Figure 4.7). Both NEAFC and the EU have prohibited all fishing activities (apart from longlining) in this area and these measures appear to have been largely well respected through time as documented in the annual WGDEC reports (e.g. ICES 2020). Due to the period of time it has been closed to mobile bottom-contacting gears and despite being originally closed as a fishery measure, it may now also be considered a closure in terms of conservation of the potentially recovered benthic habitats it contains. However, while the RHB is routinely re-established each year by the EU and NEAFC there is a possibility it could lapse in the future if parties fail to agree (Jones et al. 2018).

4.2.3.2. VME closures

In response to calls from the UNGA and following the criteria established by the FAO for VMEs, NEAFC contracted ICES to advise on the location of VMEs in the NE Atlantic. ICES worked closely with Scottish and Spanish fishing industries and drew on scientific survey data for the region to suggest areas for closure (Johnson et al. 2019). NEAFC began closing areas for the protection of VMEs in 2007, with several of these areas occurring on the Rockall Bank plateau (Figure 4.7). Each year, NEAFC receives advice from ICES, based on the work undertaken by its groups WGDEC and WGSFD, on the location of new VME records and on the level of compliance with closed areas. This process often leads to advice for amendments to existing areas or the suggestion of new ones. Within its regulatory area, NEAFC has demarcated existing fishing areas where all types of fishing are permitted according to NEAFC’s bottom fishing regulations. Outside these existing fishing areas bottom fishing is not permitted until it can be proven that fishing operations will not cause significant adverse impact to VMEs, it has also instituted ‘move-on’ rules in the event VMEs above a certain weight threshold are encountered. For the area of Rockall Bank considered in the ATLAS case study, all areas within the NEAFC regulatory area that are not closed for the protection of VMEs (Table 4.2), or fisheries management (RHB), fall within permitted fishing areas.

Table 4.2. North-East Fisheries Commission (NEAFC) VME closures on Rockall Bank.

NEAFC VME Closure	Start year, modified
North west Rockall*	2007, 2008
South-West Rockall	2008, 2013
South-West Rockall Area 1	2013, 2015
South-West Rockall Area 2	2013, 2015
South-West Rockall Area 3	2013, 2015
Logachev Mounds	2007

* Measures implemented under EU CFP, as in EU EEZ

4.2.3.3. MPAs

Four further marine protected areas (MPAs) occur in the region; three in the UK EEZ (North West Rockall Bank MPA, East Rockall Bank MPA and West of Scotland MPA) and 1 in the Irish EEZ (South East Rockall Bank SAC) (Figure 4.7).

The North West Rockall Bank MPA and the East Rockall Bank MPA were formally designated as Special Areas of Conservation (SACs) by the UK government in 2017, under the EU Habitats Directive (EC 1992) that is transposed into UK law by The Conservation of Offshore Marine Habitats and Species Regulations 2017 (UK Gov 2017). The Joint Nature Conservation Committee (JNCC) is a public body in the UK that advises the UK Government and devolved administrations that is responsible for conservation advice in the UK offshore area (12 – 200 nm) including Rockall Bank and associated UK MPAs. The North West Rockall Bank MPA was designated based on the presence of Annex I ‘biogenic reef’ and ‘stony reef’ habitat, where sizeable patches of the cold-water coral *Lophelia pertusa* occur with associated species (e.g. cup corals, serpulid worms, sponges etc.) (JNCC 2020b c). The boundary of the North West Rockall Bank MPA closely follows the boundary of the NEAFC / EU CFP North West Rockall VME closure, and encloses seabed between the depths of 102 m to 428 m below sea level. The management measures for this site are provided under the EU CFP, where it is prohibited to conduct bottom trawling or fishing with static gear in the site (EU 2013).

The East Rockall Bank MPA contains all three types of Annex I reef habitat: ‘bedrock reef’, ‘stony reef’ and ‘biogenic reef’ and also hosts the OSPAR Threatened and/or Declining habitats ‘deep-sea sponge aggregations’ and ‘coral gardens’. These reefs support a diverse range of fauna, including clumps of *Lophelia pertusa*, saddle oysters, brachiopods, Stylasterids, gorgonians, lace corals, black corals, cup corals (JNCC 2020a). The depth range within the East Rockall Bank MPA site ranges from 120 m on top of the Bank, down to 1,730 m in Rockall Trough. Management measures within the site are provided for by EU regulations: Article 8 of the EU 800 m trawling ban, which came into force on 13th January 2017 and sets 800 m as the maximum depth at which trawling can take place in the EU EEZ (EC 2016); Article 9 of this resolution also defines rules for fishing between 400 m – 800 m where VMEs occur or are likely to; fishing with bottom-set gillnets, entangling nets and trammel nets below 200 m is restricted and below 600 m is prohibited, for the protection of deep-water sharks (EC 2019), this regulation is applicable throughout the EU and NEAFC areas (JNCC 2020a). This means that the any portion of Rockall Bank that lies below 200 m has at least some restrictions in place for certain fishing gears, and for those areas within the EU EEZ and below 800 m depth, mobile bottom-contacting gears are prohibited.

The West of Scotland MPA, which is a deep-sea marine reserve and the largest MPA in Europe was designated in September 2020, under the Marine and Coastal Access Act (2009) (UK Gov 2009). The MPA boundary follows the 800 m depth contour in the Rockall Trough, bounded by the UK EEZ to the north and south, the UK continental shelf to the east and Rockall Bank to the west, with the deepest portion 2,500 m below sea level. It has been designated to protect habitat features (e.g. coral gardens, cold-water coral reefs, burrowed mud, seamounts and seamount communities), but also protects species of fish, including sharks (e.g. blue ling (*Molva dypterygia*), leafscale gulper shark (*Centrophorus squamosus*) /

gulper shark (*Centrophorus granulosus*), orange roughy (*Hoplosthus atlanticus*). The management measures within the West of Scotland MPA, where there is a ban on trawling rely on the aforementioned European regulations.

The South East Rockall Bank SAC lies within the Irish EEZ and was designated in 2016 under the EU Habitats Directive. It encompasses complex seabed features (e.g. escarpments, steep inclines, vertical walls, overhangs and caves) at depths between 500 – 1500 m on the south east slopes of Rockall Bank. These features support a diverse range of fauna, including sponges, cold-water corals, black corals, gorgonians, sea pens (NPWS 2020). And while there is no management plan in place for the site, it falls within the EU EEZ and the majority of the area lies deeper than 800 m where demersal trawling is prohibited.

4.2.3.4. Existing management plans (ABNJ)

Fisheries: there is no agreed management for the main target species (haddock) in the ABNJ. An area of Rockall Bank is closed to trawl fisheries for purpose of protecting juvenile haddock (red box in Figure 4.8). There is no depth restriction to bottom fishing within the ABNJ, however, fishing is only permitted within existing fishing areas (see Figure 4.8).

Conservation: NEAFC have adopted a series of spatial measures and regulations for bottom fishing in an attempt to protect VMEs in the area (Figure 4.8). Because the seabed of this area lies in the extended continental shelf claim of the UK, there are also some UK/EU protective measures for the seabed in this area. Some of these overlap with the NEAFC measures, while others are mutually exclusive (Figure 4.8).

Figure 4.8. Map showing the Rockall area and NEAFC management measures that apply to the ABNJ. Pink polygons are existing fishing areas (or fishing footprint). Black dashed line polygons are areas closed to protect VMEs. Red dashed line square is the so called Haddock Box that is a fisheries closure (not a VME closure). Grey solid line is the divide between the NEAFC regulatory area (ABNJ) and the EEZs of various countries. Yellow polygon is the approximate boundary of the SMA.

4.2.3.5. Existing management plans (EU EEZ)

Fisheries: management by Total Allowable Catch (TAC) applies to catches in the EU section of Rockall bank. Rockall haddock is assessed separate from other Haddock stocks, but for other species, e.g., Monkfish they are assessed as part of the western waters stock that includes the continental shelf west of Scotland. A new deep-sea fishing regulation that came into effect in 2017 does not permit bottom trawling at depths greater than 800m.

Conservation: A range of spatial protective measures have been implemented including Special Areas of Conservation and Marine Protected Areas (Figure 4.7).

4.3. Select indicators and benchmarks (MESMA Step 3)

4.3.1. MSFD Indicators

The EU's Marine Strategy Framework (MSFD) seeks to achieve Good Environmental Status (GES) in European seas by 2020 and forms the environmental pillar of the EU's Integrated European Maritime Policy, complementing its socio-economic aspects (EC 2008). It does this by setting out 11 high-level descriptors with accompanying criteria, against which achievement of GES can be evaluated, the 11 descriptors are; D1: Biodiversity, D2: Non-indigenous species, D3: Commercial fish and shellfish, D4: Food webs, D5: Eutrophication, D6: Sea-floor integrity, D7: Hydrographic conditions, D8: Contaminants, D9: Contaminants in seafood, D10: Marine litter, and D11: Energy (including underwater noise).

4.3.2. MSFD in the deep-sea

ATLAS undertook ambitious work that has contributed to the implementation of the MSFD in the deep North Atlantic. It did this by carrying out an assessment of the environmental status of nine ATLAS case studies located within European waters, including the Rockall Bank case study, for academic purposes. This work has been presented in full as an ATLAS Deliverable 3.1: Good Environmental Status and Biodiversity Assessments, and in Kazanidis et al. (2020). It focussed on five of the eleven descriptors: D1: Biodiversity, D3: Commercial species, D4: Food webs, D6: Seafloor integrity and D10: Marine litter. Adopting an indicator-based approach to evaluate GES, it applied the Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool (NEAT) (Berg et al. 2016). NEAT was developed by the EU FP7 DEVOTES project for the specific purpose of addressing GES, it is under continual development and has a large list of indicators, but can accommodate more and has a track record of being implemented in assessments. ATLAS defined GES for the deep sea as meaning:

“the extraction of living marine resources is occurring at sustainable levels and the extraction of non-living resources does not produce significant adverse impacts that can cause serious harm in the whole ecosystem, i.e. the levels of extraction ensure the continued delivery of goods and services for future generations. In particular, deep-sea GES is achieved when habitat-forming species are in a ‘good’ condition, as defined by acting as biodiversity hotspots and ensuring the functionality of the system, including the associated benthic, suprabenthic and demersal components. Areas dominated by soft sediments (e.g. the abyssal plains) maintain biodiversity at a level that ensures persistence of functional groups and thus ecosystem function. Impacts on the seabed and their effects on benthos and fish (commercial and non-commercial species) do not increase the risk of an altered or lost

ecosystem functioning, ensuring the sustainable use of deep-sea resources and the continued resilience of ecosystems in the face of a changing climate.”

4.3.3. Good Environmental Status at the Rockall Bank

The Rockall Bank case study was divided into 4 spatial assessment units (SAUs), based on depth, for analysis using NEAT (Figure 4. 9). Three GES Descriptors were considered for the Rockall Bank case study; D1 (Biodiversity is maintained), D4 (marine food web components) and D6 (sea floor integrity ensures functioning of the ecosystem). With 80 indicators used across the case study in total. Descriptor 1 was assessed for each SAU using the *Abundance of non-commercial demersal fish and cephalopods* indicator, for 6 species of fish (e.g. Blue skate, *Dipturus flossada*), resulting in 24 instances of this indicator across the case study (i.e. 6 for each SAU). For Descriptor 4, the following indicators were used across each SAU; *Species richness of non-commercial fish* (4 in total); *Species richness of benthos* (4 in total); *Species diversity (Shannon index) of non-commercial fish* (4 in total); *Biomass of selected fish species*: with 9 species considered (e.g. monkfish (*Lophius piscatorius*)) (36 in total). Descriptor 6 was considered using the indicators; *Areal extent of human affected area* (4 in total) and *Areal extent of protected sea areas* (4 in total).

Figure 4.9. Division of the Rockall Bank case study area into the 4 SAUs where GES was assessed.

The overall result of the NEAT analysis for the Rockall Bank case study suggests it is in *poor* environmental status. This was the first attempt at assessing GES at the broad scale of Rockall Bank. Assessments conducted by JNCC exist for smaller areas of the bank, features in the East and North West Rockall Bank Special Areas of Conservation are viewed as being in unfavourable condition (JNCC 2018a, b).

While previous reports (e.g. JNCC 2018a, b) seem to tally with the NEAT results for the case study, caution should be exercised in the interpretation of the NEAT results for Rockall Bank, for the reasons summarised below. The data set used to inform the fish-based indicators for the current assessment, i.e. the Rockall Haddock survey (years 1985 – 2017), also suggest lower values in 2017 than historical maxima for the majority of species and SAUs. The results of the NEAT analysis for Rockall Bank therefore seem align with these findings. However, the high temporal variability of the fish community on Rockall Bank, which seems to be correlated with metrics of oceanographic state, along with the fact that these were not incorporated into the current assessment, has implications for setting realistic targets for GES and hence the meaningfulness of the resulting GES assessment. Ecosystem variability has previously been identified as one of the most common critical issues complicating the implementation of MSFD (Alexander et al. 2015), and the Rockall Bank case study results further support this. Likewise, a similar view should be taken for the results based on the benthic invertebrate data due to the necessarily arbitrary setting of threshold and target values for these. Moreover, on account of the spatially and temporally heterogeneous distribution of the data, it may be more prudent to introduce a weighting scheme for NEAT that accounts for the amount of data available per SAU and not solely based on areal size.

4.4. Conduct risk analysis (MESMA Step 4)

4.4.1. Oil and gas risk analysis

There is currently no active oil and gas sector activity at Rockall although there has been a resurgence in calls for exploration in the area by the UK’s oil and gas sector (Broadley et al. 2020).

4.4.2. Cumulative Effect Assessment (CEA) of fishing activities

Figure 4.10. Comparison of the average spatial footprint of bottom contacting fishing activity in the Rockall Bank case study from the year 2016 based on A) Swept Area Ratio (SAR) as calculated from analysis of VMS/logbook data (ICES,2018), and B) the associated cumulative impacts on benthic habitats resulting from the concomitant pressures.

Fishing appears to be most intense at the shallower summit of the Rockall Bank and along the western flank (Figure 4.10).

4.5. Assessment of findings against operational objectives: Blue Growth scenarios (MESMA Step 5)

4.5.1. Protect areas where VME are known to occur from bottom fishing activity as part of an existing or expanded network of marine protected areas while maintaining current fisheries at close to current levels.

4.5.1.1. Baseline assessment of the effectiveness of current conservation measures

Figure 4.11. Baseline assessment of the degree of protection offered by existing conservation management measures in the Rockall Bank to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicate habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The primary function of fisheries closures on the Rockall Bank is to protect vulnerable marine ecosystems (VME) and they appear to do a very good job exceeding 30% protection for all and 50% for three of the target indicator species. It's interesting to note that *Paragorgia arborea* is well protected here in comparison with the Flemish Cap (based on predicted species distribution)(cf. Section 2.5.1.1). The closures also substantially protect fish habitat (modelled) and EUNIS broad scale habitats (with the exception of A5.15 - deep circalittoral coarse sediment and A5.27 - deep circalittoral sand at the top of the bank).

4.5.1.2. Systematic planning for protection of conservation features by area – Scenario 1.

In order to investigate how systematic conservation planning can be best applied for the Rockall Bank case study, planning units were created as a 5 km² rectangular grid (n = 1662) and mean fishing values were sampled for each grid square based on VMS data taken from the International Council for the Exploration of the Sea (ICES) for the period from 2009-2016 (Figure 4.12).

Figure 4.12. The average value of the planning units in the Rockall Bank case study based on the ICES VMS data averaged across an 8-year period (2009 – 2016).

The 120 ecosystem components described above (EUSEaMap habitats, VME indicators and habitats, modelled outputs and information of fish distributions) were included in the scenarios to guide spatial prioritisations. Within the conservation literature, there are several recommendations as to what should be the optimal target percentage to use for conserving biodiversity and associated habitats. Here, we construct a range of SCP scenarios, with the conservation targets for each set at 10, 30 and 50%. These targets were based on achieving a representative selection of the ecosystem components, rather than solely on area. The overall goal of this analysis is to assess the economic costs of implementing conservation scenarios in relation to fishing and a hypothetical oil and gas scenario in the Rockall Bank case study. This is measured economically as lost revenue from fishing, by far the main anthropogenic and economic activity undertaken at Rockall, based on the value of planning units derived from the ICES VMS value data. All scenarios presented use proportional decisions; a flexible method used within SCP whereby a fraction of a particular planning unit can be selected. This is opposed to the default option of selecting the entire planning unit (a binary decision) which can lead to greater efficiency in providing solutions (Hanson et al. 2020). 100 simulations were completed for each scenario and conservation target (10, 30, 50%), with the

final simulation being the most cost effective. Boundary penalties are an additional dynamic in Systematic Conservation Planning. They are added into conservation planning scenarios with the aim of favouring solutions which have planning units clumped together in continuous areas (Hanson et al, 2020). The higher the penalty value used in a scenario, then the greater the amount of spatial clumping will occur in the solution, the smaller the penalty value the less clumping there will be in a solution. A sensitivity analysis of appropriate boundary penalties was investigated and a value of 0.01 was judged to be the most appropriate at balancing the level of clumping in the solutions.

To account for existing spatially managed areas at Rockall Bank, planning units overlying these areas were “locked in”. Such “locked in constraints” ensure that certain planning units are selected in the outputs of any given scenario. Similarly, areas which have been degraded or deemed unsuitable for conserving biodiversity (e.g. due to an oil spill) in the scenarios are given a “locked out” status, so they are not selected for conservation purposes. Incorporating these “locked in” and “locked out” constraints in our scenarios facilitates construction of real-world conservation marine spatial planning exercises (Hanson et al, 2020). In all the scenarios, the model will ‘purchase’ either all of the area within a given planning unit, a fraction of a particular planning unit, or none of a particular planning unit. Each scenario obtains a solution on how much it would cost, based on the planning unit value, to select the planning units required to reach the conservation target (i.e. close them to fishing). All scenarios used the minimum set objective, which minimizes the cost of the solution whilst ensuring that all targets are met using the ‘prioritizR’ R package (Hanson et al, 2020). Analyses were conducted using Gurobi software, a state-of-the-art optimization solver and the most efficient solver in SCP scenario testing.

When only the managed areas concerned primarily with nature conservation are included as locked in, and the fishery management area (i.e. the Rockall Haddock Box (RHB)) is not explicitly included in the model, the solutions become less expensive than when the RHB is explicitly included (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3. The cost and percentage of the case study area (%T) associated with reaching the conservation targets in Scenario 1.

Conservation target (%)	Cost (€)	%T
10	738K	43.8
30	1.15M	48.37
50	1.84M	58.54

The selection of planning units across the conservation targets with only conservation areas locked into the models are given in Figure 4.13.

Figure 4.13. Planning units selected during Scenario 1 for A: 10%, B: 30% and C: 50% conservation targets.

4.5.1.3. Systematic planning for protection of conservation features while minimizing the impact on current fishing activities – Scenario 2.

When the spatially managed areas in place within the Rockall Bank case study (i.e. the Rockall Haddock Box, NEAFC VME closures, MPAs and SACs and > 800 m in EU EEZ, (see Table 4.4) were prioritised in the simulations, the costs to protect 10, 30 and 50 % of the ecosystem components were: €1.13 m, €1.43 m, and €2.02 m, respectively. In terms of the percentage of the total case study area required to meet these conservation targets; 51.08% was required to conserve 10% of biodiversity, 51.99% for 30% and 59.15% for 50% (Figure 4.14). The planning units selected for each of the conservation targets are presented in Figures 4.14 and 4.15.

Table 4.4. The cost and percentage of the case study area (%T) associated with reaching the conservation targets within Scenario 2.

Conservation target (%)	Cost (Millions of €)	%T
10	1.13	51.08
30	1.43	51.99
50	2.02	59.15

Figure 4.14. Planning units selected during scenario 2 for A: 10% conservation target.

Figure 4.15. Planning units selected during Scenario 2 for B: 30% and C: 50% conservation targets.

4.5.1.4. Systematic planning for 10% protection of all conservation features while minimizing the impact on current fishing activities, taking into account climate change effects and the importance of the SDM at basin scale for conservation – Scenario 4.

Figure 4.16. The degree of protection offered under SCP Scenario 4 (10% target with a trawling impact penalty of 0-100%, climate change penalty of 0-100% and basin scale importance discount of 0-25%) to: i) EUNIS broad-scale habitats, ii) predicted VME habitat and iii) predicted fish habitat. Hatched bars indicated habitat not present in the SMA. Bar chart y-axis shows the percentage conservation cover attained.

The output of this scenario (Figure 4.16) demonstrates how well the Rockall Bank is managed already with only a small area on the top of bank highlighted to address the shortfall in EUNIS A5.15 - deep circalittoral coarse sediment and A5.27 - deep circalittoral sand habitat picked up in the audit in of current closure effectiveness (4.5.1.1 above).

4.5.2. Assess potential future impacts of oil and gas developments – Scenario 3.

While there is currently no oil and gas sector activity within the Rockall Bank case study, and any development may be decades away (Schofield, *pers. comm.*), renewed interest in potential oil and gas reserves in the general area made including a ‘worse-case’ hypothetical scenario a worthwhile exercise. Five potential release sites, based on expert knowledge of potential hydrocarbon bearing geology, were selected at Rockall Bank (Schofield et al, 2017 & Schofield, *pers. comm.*). Seasonality can effect prevailing current and wind patterns (e.g. Ruprich-Robert & Cassou 2015), and subsequently the forcing in any Eulerian/Lagrangian particle tracking simulations. We, therefore, modelled oil spills with release from the 5 sites across 4 seasons using the General NOAA Operational Modelling Environment (GNOME) suite (Beegle-Krause 2001) (Figure 4.17 A). The model was forced using oceanographic

velocity fields from the Atlantic - European North West Shelf - Ocean Physics Analysis and Forecast model and EA7 Analysis winds data (Marine Copernicus 2020, <https://marine.copernicus.eu/>). Oil spill simulations during 2018 – 2019 were conducted for 3-month (90 day) periods: winter (December 2018 – February 2019), spring (March 2019 – May 2019), summer (June 2019 – August 2019) and autumn (September 2019 – November 2019). Any planning units within the Rockall Bank case study that intersected with the concave hull polygon derived from the modelled oil distribution were excluded (locked out) of the prioritisation simulations (e.g. Figure 4.17 B – E).

Figure 4.17. A. The five release sites used in the oil spill modelling; B. The resulting oil distribution (Autumn simulation); C. A concave hull polygon for area affected in the Rockall Bank case study (Autumn simulation); D. Winter concave hull polygon; E. Spring concave hull polygon and F. Summer concave hull polygon.

The costs associated with reaching the conservation targets when planning units are locked out of the models on account of being impacted by an oil spill, across each season (Table 4.5), are lower than the respective costs in Scenario 1 (Table 4.3) and higher than in Scenario 2 (Table 4.4).

Table 4.5. Costs due to interaction of simulated oil spill (by season) with planning units in case study on meeting the conservation targets (Targets (%))

Targets (%)	Winter Oil Spill (€)	Autumn Oil Spill (€)	Summer Oil Spill (€)	Spring Oil Spill (€)
10	963K	926M	1.02M	842K
30	1.28M	1.26M	1.32M	1.17M
50	1.92M	2.02M	1.92M	1.92M

The costs associated with reaching the conservation targets when planning units are locked out of the models on account of being impacted by an oil spill, across each season (Table 4.5), are lower than the respective costs in Scenario 1 (Table 4.3) and higher than in Scenario 2 (Table 4.4).

Figure 4.18. Planning units selected for conservation targets (left: 10%, middle: 30%, right: 50%) for an oil spill simulated in autumn.

Figure 4.19. Planning units selected for conservation targets (left: 10%, middle: 30%, right: 50%) for an oil spill simulated in winter.

Figure 4.20. Planning units selected for conservation targets (left: 10%, middle: 30%, right: 50%) for an oil spill simulated in spring.

Figure 4.21. Planning units selected for conservation targets (left: 10%, middle: 30%, right: 50%) for an oil spill simulated in summer.

4.6. Evaluation of management effectiveness and recommend adaptations to current management in the light of climate change (MESMA Steps 6 and 7).

Here we applied a SCP approach to assess how a range of conservation targets, set at protecting 10, 30 and 50 % of included ecosystem components, within the ATLAS Rockall Bank case study are being met by the current management regime.

Using the EUSeaMap project, we included information on the broadscale physical habitat types that occur within the case study. We supplemented this with; information on the distribution of VME habitats and indicator species from the ICES VME database, outputs from predictive distribution models and information on the distribution of fish across the case study. Economic information on the major economic activity undertaken within the case study – fishing – were used to give an indication of the costs involved in achieving the conservations targets. The effectiveness of the current management regime within the case study was assessed by including spatially managed areas that are in place for fisheries and nature conservation purposes. A further hypothetical situation that considered oil and gas as a potential growth sector in the region, was also evaluated in terms of its potential impact on fisheries and conservation.

Scenario 1 – Conservation

When the nature conservation areas within the case study are prioritised by the DST models (Scenario 2), but the RHB isn't (Scenario 1), the total area of the case study selected for conservation at the 10 % target drops to 44 %, with an associated cost of €738,000). This is a reduction of ~35 % in the associated cost compared to when the RHB is explicitly included in the SCP simulations. While not as large, reductions in the total area selected and associated costs are also observed for the 30 % target (48.37 % of the case study area, costing €1,150,000) and 50 % target (59 %, €1,840,000) in Scenario 1 in comparison to Scenario 2. The spatial arrangement of planning units selected by the SCP models across the conservation targets in Scenario 2 show that very few (N = 10) planning units within the RHB are selected at the 10 % target level and the pattern in the remainder of the case study is identical to those selected in the 10 % target in Scenario 2. However, this changes markedly when the conservation targets are increased to 30 and 50 %. At these higher targets, the DST models select large portions of the RHB, but again the selection patterns for both levels are very similar as those in Scenario 2 in the remainder of the case study.

The observed reductions in costs for the conservation targets in Scenario 1 as compared to Scenario 2, arise from the planning units within the RHB representing areas of value to fishers. This seemingly contradictory situation, where areas that have been closed to mobile bottom-contact fishing gears throughout the time period from which the economic data arise, can be explained in the case of the RHB by poorly-drafted regulations. Jones et al. (2018) note that for the period 2013 – 2015 the wording of the Haddock Box including the following statement: “*All fishing of Rockall haddock, except with longlines, shall be prohibited in the areas...*”. This was interpreted by fishers to be a species-specific caveat, rather than a gear-specific one, resulting in mobile bottom gears targeting other species (e.g. monkfish) in the Rockall Haddock Box during this period. The wording of the regulations was redrafted to: “*All fishing, except with longlines, shall be prohibited...*” in 2015, and subsequent to this there has been compliance, as described in the various WGDEC reports (e.g. ICES 2020).

Scenario 2 – Conservation and fisheries

As the Rockall Bank case study contains several closed areas, including these within the SCP simulations allows an assessment of how they contribute to achieving the conservation targets. When considered on the 5 km² grid of planning units, 41.27 % of the case study already falls within some form of designation (nature conservation or fishery closure). For the 10 % conservation target, with the nature conservation areas and the Rockall Haddock box locked in so they are selected by the simulations (Scenario 2), a total of 51 % of the case study area is selected for conservation at a cost of €1,130,000. The planning units selected for the 10 % conservation target in Scenario 2 include those areas within closed areas, but also those planning units at the central western and southern boundaries of the case study that are recorded as having no economic value in the landings data.

A similar pattern is observed for the 30 % conservation target in Scenario 2 (52 % of the total area of the case study selected, with a cost of €1,430,000), but with the addition of a further 10 planning units selected in the shallower central northern Rockall Bank area. The presence of physical habitats here (EUNIS codes A5.15 & A4.33) that do not occur in the rest of the case study due to the comparatively shallow depths in this area mean that, despite this containing some of the highest value planning units, these are chosen to meet the conservation targets. For the 50 % conservation target in Scenario 2, 59 % of the total case study area is selected, with an associated cost of €2,020,000. There is an expansion of the planning units selected in this scenario, particularly around the North-West Rockall VME closure / North-West Rockall MPA, close to the boundary in the north-west of the case study and again an addition of planning units in the shallower central northern Rockall Bank area.

Scenario 3 (Oil and Gas)

A further, hypothetical scenario, which investigated the effect on conservation planning from a catastrophic failure in oil and gas operations, was also conducted. An oil spill was modelled, using five release locations lying to the east of the case study and across four seasons in an effort to capture any variation in prevailing current or wind directions. Concave hull polygons were derived from the dispersal patterns of the oil and these were then used to exclude areas within the case study from the SCP models. These concave hulls were restricted to the north-east of the case study and while there were differences between the seasons (autumn and spring spills affected a larger area of the case study), only this local region was affected. The spatial arrangement of the planning units selected by the SCP models showed high fidelity, apart from those areas excluded from the analysis, to those undertaken across the conservation targets in Scenario 2. The costs of achieving the targets across the seasons are reduced when compared to those in Scenario 2. This can be explained by how the SCP models treat those cells ‘locked-out’ of the analysis in that they discount them completely as having conservation value and seek to meet the conservation targets with those planning units available. The reduced costs associated with meeting the conservation targets across the seasons in Scenario 3 compared with Scenario 2, along with the high fidelity between the arrangement of planning units selected for both, is a result of these relatively high cost areas being excluded (reduced overall cost compared to ‘locking’ them in) and the ability for the SCP models to reach the conservation targets by selecting planning units elsewhere.

Adaptive Management

Here we present an evaluation of how the current management regime on Rockall Bank meets a range of conservation targets. Using a suite of ecosystem components and economic information on fisheries landing, we used SCP models to assess the cost / benefit of the current arrangement of spatially managed areas.

Across all scenarios and conservation targets, the DST models selected planning units from the shallower central northern bank area, which is amongst the most valuable in terms of fisheries. The models selected planning units in this area due to the uniquely shallow nature of the habitats here within the case study. This area falls within the UK EEZ and the habitats that are unique at the case study level, may appear less critical if considered in a wider regional context. It would be appropriate for an analysis at the regional scale to be conducted to assess the cost / benefit of instigating any conservation measures here in the wider regional context.

The Rockall Haddock Box(RHB) , an area closed for the purposes of fisheries management, appears to be important in meeting the higher conservation targets used in this study. This area has, apart from the years 2013 – 2015, been closed to commercial mobile-bottom contacting fishing gears since 2001 / 2002. Quantitative seabed imagery surveys that investigate the current state of benthic communities inside versus outside the RHB would be an interesting study on the benthic impacts of fishing pressure and recovery. Indeed, this was an objective of a recent Marine Scotland Science survey aboard the MRV *Scotia* (survey code 1420S; 22nd September – 9th October, 2020). Unfortunately, weather conditions were too poor to use the drop-camera system for the full random stratified survey that was planned. However, two semi-quantitative towed video transects of 10 km each, were carried out inside and outside the north-west portion of the RHB. These data, once analysed, may give an indication on the state of the benthic environment within the RHB. This area, given it is already effectively acting as a closure, along with its apparent importance in meeting the higher conservation targets considered here, may be a good candidate for consideration as a conservation closure.

Across all scenarios tested, the SCP models consistently selected areas that had no value associated with the planning units outside of existing areal closures as priorities for conservation. These areas were predominantly located in the deeper areas to western and southern boundaries of the case study in international waters. If fishing effort within these areas has indeed been low, targeted surveys of these areas using towed cameras may provide supporting evidence for an expansion of the South-West Rockall closure.

4.7. Governance (MESMA Step 8)

Rockall Bank has experienced a rapid expansion in the use of area-based management tools over the last twenty years. Given the first spatially managed area was put in place in 2001/2002 for the purposes of fisheries management, and the first conservation areas in 2007, management of the area has come a long way in a relatively short time. However, the recent development of spatially managed areas is somewhat juxtaposed to the long history of exploitation at Rockall Bank. This long history will have undoubtedly impacted vulnerable habitats within the case study, and the life-history traits of many deep-sea benthic organisms are such that recovery rates are expected to be extremely protracted. Protection of VMEs in

international waters in the NE Atlantic typically follow a pathway where submission of records to the annual ICES VME data call is made, these are considered and reported on during the annual joint NAFO / ICES WGDEC meeting, advice is then drafted and approved before being passed from ICES to NEAFC with recommendations and NEAFC implements closures. This is generally an efficient process that could see field observation receive protection within a year, but as Johnson et al. (2019) note, this process runs much more quickly where records and fishing activity don't overlap spatially. A similar process is currently being developed within EU waters to protect VMEs, with the Workshop on EU regulatory area options for VME protection (WKEUVME) held from 18–28 May 2020. The fishery at Rockall Bank remains profitable and is managed by a TAC limit based on ICES advice which is conditioned on the Maximum Sustainable Yield approach (e.g. ICES 2019). It was certified as meeting the standards of sustainability by the Marine Stewardship Council in 2018 (Jones et al. 2018, Johnson et al. 2019). The tendency for areas of high landings value to co-occur with the boundaries of closed areas (Figure 4. 12), suggest a possible spill over effect and it would be interesting to evaluate these conservation areas in terms of their benefit to the fishery.

Johnson et al. (2019) review marine governance in the wider Hatton-Rockall region, describing it as a *super wicked* problem, where the complex institutional landscape makes developing a holistic sustainable use management plan difficult. The analyses presented here, for the portion of Rockall Bank considered, suggest that the area-based management tools arising from this complex landscape of regulatory drivers and instruments, function in a very large part to meet conservation targets suggested in the literature, even the more ambitious ones. Ultimately, this could be a more efficient and conscious process if plans were integrated across the various stakeholders in the region, something that Johnson et al. (2019) also note would represent a *super wicked* solution.

4.8. References

- Alexander KA, Kershaw P, Cooper P, Gilbert AJ, Hall-Spencer JM, Heymans JJ, Kannen A, Los HJ, O'Higgins T, O'Mahony C, others (2015) Challenges of achieving good environmental status in the Northeast Atlantic. *Ecol Soc* 20.
- Ban NC, Klein CJ (2009) Spatial socioeconomic data as a cost in systematic marine conservation planning. *Conserv Lett* 2:206–215.
- Beegle-Krause J (2001) General NOAA oil modelling environment (GNOME): a new spill trajectory model. *Int Oil Spill Conf Proc* 2001:865–871.
- Berg T, Murray C, Carstensen J, Andersen JH (2016) NEAT–Nested Environmental status Assessment Tool. Manual–Version 1:38.
- Berx B, Payne MR (2017) The Sub-Polar Gyre Index – a community data set for application in fisheries and environment research. *Earth Syst Sci Data* 9:259–266.
- Broadley L, Schofield N, Jolley D, Howell J, Underhill JR (2020) UK Rockall prospectivity: re-awakening exploration in a frontier basin. *Pet Geosci* 26:247–271.
- Burgman MA, Possingham HP, Lynch AJJ, Keith DA, McCarthy MA, Hopper SD, Drury WL, Passioura JA, Devries RJ (2001) A Method for Setting the Size of Plant Conservation Target Areas. *Conserv Biol* 15:603–616.
- Clark MR, Althaus F, Schlacher TA, Williams A, Bowden DA, Rowden AA (2016) The impacts of deep-sea fisheries on benthic communities: a review. *ICES J Mar Sci* 73:i51–i69.
- EC (1992) Council Directive 92/43/EEC of 21 May 1992 on the conservation of natural habitats and of wild fauna and flora.
- EC (2008) Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive) (Text with EEA relevance).
- EC (2016) Regulation (EU) 2016/2336 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2016 establishing specific conditions for fishing for deep-sea stocks in the north-east Atlantic and provisions

- for fishing in international waters of the north-east Atlantic and repealing Council Regulation (EC) No 2347/2002.
- EC (2019) Regulation (EU) 2019/1241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on the conservation of fisheries resources and the protection of marine ecosystems through technical measures, amending Council Regulations (EC) No 1967/2006, (EC) No 1224/2009 and Regulations (EU) No 1380/2013, (EU) 2016/1139, (EU) 2018/973, (EU) 2019/472 and (EU) 2019/1022 of the European Parliament and of the Council, and repealing Council Regulations (EC) No 894/97, (EC) No 850/98, (EC) No 2549/2000, (EC) No 254/2002, (EC) No 812/2004 and (EC) No 2187/2005.
- Ehler C (2018) Marine Spatial Planning: an idea whose time has come.
- EU (2013) Regulation (EU) No 227/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 March 2013 amending Council Regulation (EC) No 850/98 for the conservation of fishery resources through technical measures for the protection of juveniles of marine organisms and Council Regulation (EC) No 1434/98 specifying conditions under which herring may be landed for industrial purposes other than direct human consumption.
- FAO (2009) Report of the Technical Consultation on International Guidelines for the Management of Deep-sea Fisheries in the High Seas. Rome, 4th February and 25th August 2008. Food Agric Organ UN Fish Aquac Rep 881:86.
- Foley MM, Halpern BS, Micheli F, Armsby MH, Caldwell MR, Crain CM, Prahler E, Rohr N, Sivas D, Beck MW, Carr MH, Crowder LB, Emmett Duffy J, Hacker SD, McLeod KL, Palumbi SR, Peterson CH, Regan HM, Ruckelshaus MH, Sandifer PA, Steneck RS (2010) Guiding ecological principles for marine spatial planning. *Mar Policy* 34:955–966.
- Gilliland PM, Laffoley D (2008) Key elements and steps in the process of developing ecosystem-based marine spatial planning. *Mar Policy* 32:787–796.
- Halpern BS, Walbridge S, Selkoe KA, Kappel CV, Micheli F, D'Agrosa C, Bruno JF, Casey KS, Ebert C, Fox HE, Fujita R, Heinemann D, Lenihan HS, Madin EMP, Perry MT, Selig ER, Spalding M, Steneck R, Watson R (2008) A Global Map of Human Impact on Marine Ecosystems. *Science* 319:948–952.
- Hanson J, Schuster R, Morrell N, Strimas-Mackey M, Watts M, Arcese P, Bennett J, Possingham H (2020) *Prioritizr: Systematic Conservation Prioritization in R*.
- Hátún H, Payne MR, Beaugrand G, Reid PC, Sandø AB, Drange H, Hansen B, Jacobsen JA, Bloch D (2009) Large bio-geographical shifts in the north-eastern Atlantic Ocean: From the subpolar gyre, via plankton, to blue whiting and pilot whales. *Prog Oceanogr* 80:149–162.
- Hiddink JG, Jennings S, Sciberras M, Szostek CL, Hughes KM, Ellis N, Rijnsdorp AD, McConnaughey RA, Mazar T, Hilborn R, Collie JS, Pitcher CR, Amoroso RO, Parma AM, Suuronen P, Kaiser MJ (2017) Global analysis of depletion and recovery of seabed biota after bottom trawling disturbance. *Proc Natl Acad Sci*.
- ICES (2019) Haddock (*Melanogrammus aeglefinus*) in Division 6.b (Rockall).
- ICES (2020) ICES NAFO Joint Working Group on Deep-water Ecology (WGDEC).
- JNCC (2020a) East Rockall Bank MPA | JNCC - Adviser to Government on Nature Conservation. <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/east-rockall-bank-mpa/#site-timeline> (accessed December 1, 2020)
- JNCC (2020b) North West Rockall Bank MPA | JNCC - Adviser to Government on Nature Conservation. <https://jncc.gov.uk/our-work/north-west-rockall-bank-mpa/#site-timeline> (accessed December 1, 2020)
- JNCC (2020c) North West Rockall Bank MPA – Conservation Advice | JNCC Resource Hub. <https://hub.jncc.gov.uk/assets/7af4ea89-5edf-43dd-bac0-218be54a26ad#NWRBank-2-Conservation-Objectives-V1.0.pdf> (accessed December 1, 2020)
- JNCC (2018a) Statements on conservation benefits, condition & conservation measures for East Rockall Bank Special Area of Conservation.
- JNCC (2018b) Statements on conservation benefits, condition & conservation measures for North West Rockall Bank Special Area of Conservation.
- Johnson DE, Barrio Froján C, Neat F, Van Oevelen D, Stirling D, Gubbins MJ, Roberts JM (2019) Rockall and Hatton: Resolving a Super Wicked Marine Governance Problem in the High Seas of the Northeast Atlantic Ocean. *Front Mar Sci* 6.
- Jones H, Cook R, Gascoigne J, Hønneland G (2018) Marine Stewardship Council (MSC) Public Comment Draft Report SFSAG Rockall haddock On behalf of Scottish Fisheries Sustainable Accreditation Group (SFSAG). MSC.
- Kaiser MJ, Clarke KR, Hinz H, Austen MCV, Somerfield PJ, Karakassis I (2006) Global analysis of response and recovery of benthic biota to fishing. *Mar Ecol Prog Ser* 311:1–14.
- Kazanidis G, Orejas C, Borja A, Kenchington E, Henry L-A, Callery O, Carreiro-Silva M, Egilsdottir H, Giacomello E, Grehan A, Menot L, Morato T, Ragnarsson SÁ, Rueda JL, Stirling D, Stratmann T, van Oevelen D, Palialexis A, Johnson D, Roberts JM (2020) Assessing the environmental status of selected North Atlantic deep-sea ecosystems. *Ecol Indic* 119:106624.

- Kenchington EL, Kenchington TJ, Henry L-A, Fuller S, Gonzalez P (2007) Multi-decadal changes in the megabenthos of the Bay of Fundy: The effects of fishing. *J Sea Res* 58:220–240.
- Kidd S, Calado H, Gee K, Gilek M, Saunders F (2020) Marine Spatial Planning and sustainability: Examining the roles of integration - Scale, policies, stakeholders and knowledge. *Ocean Coast Manag* 191:105182.
- Kroodasma DA, Mayorga J, Hochberg T, Miller NA, Boerder K, Ferretti F, Wilson A, Bergman B, White TD, Block BA, Woods P, Sullivan B, Costello C, Worm B (2018) Tracking the global footprint of fisheries. *Science* 359:904–908.
- Margules CR, Pressey RL (2000) Systematic conservation planning. *Nature* 405:243–253.
- McGrath T, Nolan G, McGovern E (2012) Chemical characteristics of water masses in the Rockall Trough. *Deep Sea Res Part Oceanogr Res Pap* 61:57–73.
- McIntosh EJ, Pressey RL, Lloyd S, Smith RJ, Grenyer R (2017) The Impact of Systematic Conservation Planning. *Annu Rev Environ Resour* 42:677–697.
- Morato T, Pham CK, Pinto C, Golding N, Ardron JA, Durán Muñoz P, Neat F (2018) A Multi Criteria Assessment Method for Identifying Vulnerable Marine Ecosystems in the North-East Atlantic. *Front Mar Sci* 5.
- Naidoo R, Balmford A, Ferraro PJ, Polasky S, Ricketts TH, Rouget M (2006) Integrating economic costs into conservation planning. *Trends Ecol Evol* 21:681–687.
- Neat F, Campbell N (2011) Demersal fish diversity of the isolated Rockall plateau compared with the adjacent west coast shelf of Scotland. *Biol J Linn Soc* 104:138–147.
- Newton AW, Peach KJ, Coull KA, Gault M, Needle CL (2008) Rockall and the Scottish haddock fishery. *Fish Res* 94:133–140.
- NPWS (2020) South-east Rockall Bank SAC | National Parks & Wildlife Service. <https://www.npws.ie/protected-sites/sac/003002> (accessed December 2, 2020)
- Pomeroy R, Douvère F (2008) The engagement of stakeholders in the marine spatial planning process. *Mar Policy* 32:816–822.
- Populus J, Vasquez M, Albrecht J, Manca E, Agnesi S, Al Hamdani Z, Andersen J, Annunziatellis A, Bekkby T, Bruschi A, Doncheva V, Drakopoulou V, Duncan G, Inghilesi R, Kyriakidou C, Lalli F, Lillis H, Mo G, Muresan M, Salomidi M, Sakellariou D, Simboura M, Teaca A, Tezcan D, Todorova V, Tunesi L (2017) EUSeaMap. A European broad-scale seabed habitat map.
- Qiu W, Jones PJS (2013) The emerging policy landscape for marine spatial planning in Europe. *Mar Policy* 39:182–190.
- Roberts JM, Henry L-A, Long D, Hartley JP (2008) Cold-water coral reef frameworks, megafaunal communities and evidence for coral carbonate mounds on the Hatton Bank, north east Atlantic. *Facies* 54:297–316.
- Ruprich-Robert Y, Cassou C (2015) Combined influences of seasonal East Atlantic Pattern and North Atlantic Oscillation to excite Atlantic multidecadal variability in a climate model. *Clim Dyn* 44:229–253.
- Schofield N, Jolley D, Holford S, Archer S, Watson D, Hartley A, Howell J, Muirhead D, Underhill J, Green P (2018) Challenges of future exploration within the UK Rockall Basin. In: *Geological Society, London, Petroleum Geology Conference series*. Geological Society of London, p 211–229
- Swartz W, Sala E, Tracey S, Watson R, Pauly D, Sandin SA (2010) The Spatial Expansion and Ecological Footprint of Fisheries (1950 to Present). *PLoS ONE* 5:12.
- UK Gov (2009) Marine and Coastal Access Act 2009. Statute Law Database.
- UK Gov (2017) The Conservation of Habitats and Species Regulations 2017. Queen’s Printer of Acts of Parliament.
- UNGA (2006) Resolution 61/105. Sustainable Fisheries, Including Through the 1995 Agreement for the Implementation of the Provisions of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea of 10 December 1982 Relating to the Conservation and Management of Straddling Fish Stocks and Highly Migratory Fish Stocks, and Related Instruments.
- Watson RA, Tidd A (2018) Mapping nearly a century and a half of global marine fishing: 1869–2015. *Mar Policy* 93:171–177.
- Yiallourides C (2018) It takes four to tango: Quadrilateral boundary negotiations in the North-East Atlantic. *Mar Policy* 87:78–83.

5. Summary Conclusions

5.1. MESMA Marine Spatial Planning Framework

We tested the MESMA generic MSP framework in three ATLAS case studies: Porcupine, Rockall and Flemish Cap. Adopting the MESMA approach provided a structure and key steps to enable an assessment of the adequacy of the scientific evidence base available to support marine spatial planning at regional/local scale in the North Atlantic. While there are still issues around data sufficiency and resolution (e.g. reporting of fish catch and landings, cf. Chapter 2: Porcupine Case Study) improvements are being made (e.g. access to Global Fishing Watch data). Modelling, particularly species and habitat distribution modelling, have been used to good effect to address data gaps in this study and model outputs are amenable for use by decision support tools, particularly systematic conservation planning (see below). We have also demonstrated that it is possible to use basin scale planning outputs to inform local plans.

5.2. Systematic Conservation Planning

Systematic conservation planning is undoubtedly an invaluable tool for operationalising effective conservation management (Reside et al., 2018), however, one of the major criticisms of SCP has been the tendency for practitioners to fixate on simply ensuring that conservation features are represented in a solution MPA network, when, to effectively preserve biodiversity, there is a need for much deeper thought to be given to ensuring the persistence and long-term viability of species assemblages (Magris et al., 2014; Sarkar et al., 2009). Groves et al. (2012) proposed five approaches to considering climate-change adaptation in conservation management plans; the following lists these approaches and elaborates on how each approach was implemented in this SCP exercise.

5.2.1. Conserving the geophysical stage

It was originally proposed by (Hunter et al., 1988) that, to address considerations of climate change when seeking to conserve biodiversity in data-poor regions lacking “biological inventories”, protecting a diversity of landscape units (as defined by topography and soil types) could be an effective means of underpinning regional planning exercises. In the local SCP exercise conducted as part of this Deliverable 6.3, data layers of broad benthic habitats from the EUSeaMap (Populus et al., 2017) and Random Forest modelling outputs produced for ATLAS milestone report 30 (Mapping the Cumulative Effect of Bottom Fisheries on Benthic Habitats in 12 ATLAS Case Study Areas) were used to fulfil this role, by augmenting data on species’ distributions (SDM outputs from ATLAS Work Package 3) and bone fide records of vulnerable and threatened habitats (OSPAR database of threatened and declining habitats; ICES VME database) to ensure that no area within any of the ATLAS case studies was devoid of conservation features and consequently ignored by the SCP software because of a lack of available data in the deep-sea.

5.2.2. Protecting climate refugia

Climate refugia represent areas where changes in climate are attenuated or where biodiversity is predicted to be more resilient to such changes. In ATLAS Work Package 3, climate refugia were identified for six commercially important deep-sea fishes and six deep-sea cold-water corals in the North Atlantic Ocean. These climate refugia were used as input data both to the exercise in local-SCP described in this text, as well as the basin-scale SCP presented in ATLAS Deliverable 3.4, thus ensuring that their inclusion in any suggested MPA networks was prioritized across all scales of analysis (see 5.5, below).

5.2.3. Enhancing regional connectivity

Species' persistence depends not just on the quantity of remaining suitable habitat available, but also their ability to reach it (Reside et al., 2018). The persistence of populations also depends greatly on the movement of organisms (and genetic material) between areas of suitable habitat (e.g. larval dispersal pathways) and ensuring that appropriate consideration is given to inter-population connectivity is critically important to the design of an effective MPA network (Magris et al., 2014). Simply reducing the distances between MPAs, though it would improve connectivity, is not sufficient; to do so would greatly increase the risk that single, isolated events (of, for example, coral bleaching or anthropogenic disturbance) would adversely affect multiple MPAs, ultimately hindering future recovery (Almany et al., 2009). In the local SCP exercise conducted as part of this Deliverable 6.3, the outputs of ATLAS Work Package 1 - Deliverable 1.6, Biologically realistic Lagrangian dispersal and connectivity - and ATLAS Work Package 3 - Basin-scale systematic conservation planning: identifying suitable networks for VMEs protection - were used to ensure that areas which are highly interconnected on a basin scale (and thus form important larvae pathways and hubs that link population patches of sessile invertebrate species) were given high-priority when meeting conservation objectives at the local-scale.

5.2.4. Sustaining ecosystem process and function

One of the great challenges of considering ecosystem process and function is to identify spatial data which might be used as suitable surrogates for these processes and functions (Klein et al., 2009). Using the example of wildfire, (Leroux et al., 2007) explored how models could be used to simulate disturbance regimes that could be used in conservation planning exercises and concluded that such simulations could be useful in addressing considerations relating to other natural disturbances such as climate change. In the local SCP exercise conducted as part of this Deliverable 6.3, areas that the model predicted would maintain biodiversity in the face of climate change (based on the SDM outputs of ATLAS Work Package 3) were used to prioritise conservation of areas likely to have greater resilience to the effects of climate change thus improving the long-term viability of the suggested MPA network.

5.3. Capitalizing on opportunities emerging in response to climate change.

While the negative effects of climate change are widely and often discussed, it is also true that conditions for some species and ecosystems may also improve. In the recent ATLAS paper, Morato et al., (2020) found that, under the “business as usual” RCP 8.5 climate change scenario, there was projected to be a northwards shift of as much as $\sim 10^\circ$ in the distributions of the six commercially important fish species whose ranges were used as input data in this SCP exercise. Spatial data layers relating to the future distributions of these species were used to adjust the “cost” of planning units in all of the ATLAS case studies. In this way, areas that are predicted to experience an increase in suitability for these species over the next century are prioritized for immediate pre-emptive conservation; this could prove crucial if commercially viable stocks of such species are to become established.

In a recent review investigating the integration of connectivity and climate change into marine conservation planning, Magris et al., (2014) identified an over-reliance on addressing these issues by means of qualitative statements without quantitative specification. With the extensive oceanographic and biogeographic modelling conducted by project partners in the ATLAS project, it has been possible to use ecologically justified, quantitative data and objectives to identify priority areas for conservation in ATLAS case studies across the north Atlantic basin. Figures 5.1 - 5.10, present these priority areas and the accompanying charts provide insight into the contribution this ecologically representative network of MPAs and OECMs would

make towards achieving the ambitious conservation targets laid out in the CBD's Post-2020 Biodiversity Framework: to protect at least 30% of land and sea areas (with at least 10% under strict protection) and 60% of sites of particular importance for biodiversity (CBD, 2020).

B)

Figure 5. 1. Outputs from (A) connectivity based basin-scale SCP carried out in ATLAS Work Package 3 (Combes et al., In Press), and (B) Integration of these outputs into the local-scale SCP conducted for ATLAS Deliverable 6.3.

Figure 5.2. Case Study 1 – LoVe Observatory: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11 (10%), and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 (30%) conservation targets.

Figure 5.3. Case Study 2 – Faroe-Shetland Channel: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11 (10%), and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 (30%) conservation targets.

Figure 5. 4. Case Study 3 - Rockall Bank: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11 (10%), and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 (30%) conservation targets.

Figure 5.5. Case Study 6 – Bay of Biscay: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11 (10%), and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 (30%) conservation targets.

Figure 5.6. Case Study 7 – Gulf of Cádiz / Strait of Gibraltar: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11 (10%), and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 (30%) conservation targets.

Figure 5.7. Case Study 8 – Azores: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11 (10%), and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 (30%) conservation targets.

Figure 5. 8. Case Study 9 – Reykjanes Ridge: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11, and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 targets.

Figure 5.9. Case Study 10 – Davis Strait / Baffin Bay: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11, and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 targets.

Figure 5.10. Case Study 12 – Mid-Atlantic Canyons: The degree of protection offered (and potential associated disruption to existing demersal trawl fisheries) under (A) SCP Scenario 4 – expansion of existing MPA/OECM network to meet Aichi Target 11, and (B) expansion from Scenario 4 to meet the CBD 2030 targets.

5.4. References

- Almany, G.R., Connolly, S.R., Heath, D.D., Hogan, J.D., Jones, G.P., McCook, L.J., Mills, M., Pressey, R.L., Williamson, D.H., 2009. Connectivity, biodiversity conservation and the design of marine reserve networks for coral reefs. *Coral Reefs* 28, 339–351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00338-009-0484-x>
- Hunter, M.L., Jacobson, G.L., Webb, T., 1988. Paleoecology and the Coarse-Filter Approach to Maintaining Biological Diversity. *Conserv. Biol.* 2, 375–385. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1523-1739.1988.tb00202.x>
- Klein, C., Wilson, K., Watts, M., Stein, J., Berry, S., Carwardine, J., Smith, M.S., Mackey, B., Possingham, H., 2009. Incorporating ecological and evolutionary processes into continental-scale conservation planning. *Ecol. Appl.* 19, 206–217. <https://doi.org/10.1890/07-1684.1>
- Leroux, S.J., Schmiegelow, F.K.A., Cumming, S.G., Lessard, R.B., Nagy, J., 2007. Accounting for System Dynamics in Reserve Design. *Ecol. Appl.* 17, 1954–1966. <https://doi.org/10.1890/06-1115.1>
- Magris, R.A., Pressey, R.L., Weeks, R., Ban, N.C., 2014. Integrating connectivity and climate change into marine conservation planning. *Biol. Conserv.* 170, 207–221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2013.12.032>
- Morato, T., González-Irusta, J.-M., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Wei, C.-L., Davies, A., Sweetman, A.K., Taranto, G.H., Beazley, L., García-Alegre, A., Grehan, A., Laffargue, P., Murillo, F.J., Sacau, M., Vaz, S., Kenchington, E., Arnaud-Haond, S., Callery, O., Chimienti, G., Cordes, E., Egilsdottir, H., Freiwald, A., Gasbarro, R., Gutiérrez-Zárate, C., Gianni, M., Gilkinson, K., Hayes, V.E.W., Hebbeln, D., Hedges, K., Henry, L.-A., Johnson, D., Koen-Alonso, M., Lirette, C., Mastrototaro, F., Menot, L., Molodtsova, T., Muñoz, P.D., Orejas, C., Pennino, M.G., Puerta, P., Ragnarsson, S.Á., Ramiro-Sánchez, B., Rice, J., Rivera, J., Roberts, J.M., Ross, S.W., Rueda, J.L., Sampaio, Í., Snelgrove, P., Stirling, D., Treble, M.A., Urra, J., Vad, J., Oevelen, D. van, Watling, L., Walkusz, W., Wienberg, C., Woillez, M., Levin, L.A., Carreiro-Silva, M., 2020. Climate-induced changes in the suitable habitat of cold-water corals and commercially important deep-sea fishes in the North Atlantic. *Glob. Change Biol.* 26, 2181–2202. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.14996>
- Populus, J., Vasquez, M., Albrecht, J., Manca, E., Agnesi, S., Al Hamdani, Z., Andersen, J., Annunziatellis, A., Bekkby, T., Bruschi, A., 2017. EUSeaMap. A European broad-scale seabed habitat map.
- Reside, A.E., Butt, N., Adams, V.M., 2018. Adapting systematic conservation planning for climate change. *Biodivers. Conserv.* 27, 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-017-1442-5>
- Sarkar, S., Fuller, T., Aggarwal, A., Moffett, A., Kelley, C.D., 2009. 16. The ConsNet Software Platform for Systematic Conservation Planning.

Regional marine spatial planning to support Blue Growth while accounting for climate change

Project acronym:	ATLAS
Grant Agreement:	678760
Deliverable number:	Deliverable 6.3
Deliverable title:	Assessment of the utility of the MESMA generic framework to promote area-based management in N Atlantic case studies while accounting for climate change
Work Package:	6
Date of completion:	31/10/2020

APPENDIX

Morato, T., L. Rodrigues, G.H. Taranto, C. Dominguez-Carrió, L. Fauconnet, C.K. Pham, R. Prieto, M. Tobeña, J.M. Gonzalez-Irusta, E. Giacomello, M. Carreiro-Silva (2019). Systematic conservation planning to evaluate fisheries closures scenarios for rebuilding fish stocks in Mar da Prata. ATLAS project (GA 678760) and MapGES (ACORES-01-0145-FEDER-00056) internal report. IMAR Instituto do Mar, MARE Marine and Environmental Sciences Centre, OKEANOS Research Unit, Universidade dos Açores, Departamento de Oceanografia e Pesca. Horta, 70 pp.

Morato, T., Combes, M., Brito, J., Rodrigues, L., Dominguez-Carrió, C., Taranto, G.H., Fauconnet, L., Ramos, M., Blasco-Ferre, J., Gutiérrez-Zárate, C., Pham, C.K., Colaço, A., Gonzalez-Irusta, J.M., Giacomello, E., & Carreiro-Silva, M. (2020) Systematic conservation planning scenarios for the Azores deep-sea: draft v.11 Feb 2020. Okeanos Centre of the University of the Azores, Horta, Portugal. 274pp.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 678760 (ATLAS). This output reflects only the author's view and the European Union cannot be held responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.